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GRIMM Experimental Forming Apparatus Documentation

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1 Introduction

This document serves as a background and description for the GRIMM's systematic design and to document design decisions made to create this scaled rotary former. The core of the machine is a donated 30 HP Herbert capstan or turret lathe. This lathe was retrofitted with the necessary systems to create a machine capable of performing the repeatable flow forming of a specific cast aluminum blank, at elevated temperatures, while providing necessary process measurements. The main purpose of this document is to describe each of the subsystems, with a scope limited to design, operation and where applicable, maintenance.

The main subsystems added are shown in Fig. 1. This document is arranged with the following main sections:

1. Lathe overview
2. Blank design
3. Tooling design, including mandrel and roller assemblies
4. Heating system
5. Instrumentation, primarily focussed on the rotary DAQ module.

Figure 1: Main GRIMM modules added to the lathe to permit rotary forming experiments at elevated temperatures.

Figure 2: Main lathe features (numbered) and main axial feed trunnion bearing lubrication point

2 Lathe overview

Standard lathes have three basic elements: a spindle to which a workpiece may be affixed via a chuck, a tool stand to hold a turning tool which may be moved along bed rails to encounter the workpiece, and a tailstock on the same bed rails placed after the tool mount to support long and heavy workpieces. The tool stand is usually equipped with a feed mechanism to move the tool at a constant speed across and into the workpiece. The tailstock is usually moved into place at the start of turning and does not move.

2.1 As-received lathe description

The Herbert capstan lathe is different from this basic lathe in that there are two locations for tooling mounts, and the tailstock has been replaced by an indexable turret so that it may contain multiple turning tools and tailstocks. Furthermore, there are feeds for both the tool mount and the turret. Additionally, there is a capstan to control tooling and tailstock flex during heavy turning operations. The Herbert capstan lathe has 10 main components that are of importance as shown in Fig. 2 and described with Table 1. This lathe is preferential over other lathes because of the overall mass of the chassis, the additional support that can be found by the steady-rest.

There are four items that can be powered by the 30 HP, continuously run motor. The output from this motor is transmitted by belts to a transmission which drives the spindle and tool saddle feed, the feed system for the turret saddle, and a coolant pump. Since the turret and coolant pump are not employed

Table 1: Lathe main feature description. Numbered entries correspond to details shown on Fig. 2

1	Frame	Houses the main spindle and feed transmission(s).
2	Mast	Solid steel bar providing extra rigidity.
3	Steady rest	Communicates turret with the mast.
4	Tailstock	Adjustable workpiece support which limits axial workpiece deflection. Integrated with steady rest.
5	Toolstand location	Position on the saddle which allows mounting turning tools. Small offset lever locks the radial position of the toolstand, limiting movement of the tool slide.
6	Spindle takeoff	Workpiece/chuck mounting position. Driven end of workpiece.
7	Tool slide	Permits toolstand to move radially (along R direction) in and out of the workpiece. Locked in position by the lever indicated in (5).
8	Saddle	Permits movement of the tool slide/toolstand axially (along the z direction) along the workpiece.
9	Capstan	Permits the mounting of up to 6 different tailstocks or tailstock quills. Currently, only the integrated tailstock/steady rest are employed.
10	Turret saddle	Permits the capstan to move axially (along the z direction) independently of the main saddle.

(a) Spindle and saddle

(b) Tailstock

Figure 3: Lathe controls and lubrication points. Note that lubrication points on the saddle, indicated by the asterisk in (a), are currently total-loss oiling points.

during forming operations, drive belts were removed so that the lathe motor is only coupled to the spindle and the saddle feed.

Other features and controls of interest on the machine are shown in Fig. 3, with features further described with Table 2 and 3. These include levers and wheels to control the speed of the spindle, movement of the tool stand, tool slide and saddle, as well as actuation of the turret saddle and capstan.

2.2 Lathe spindle speed and feedrates

The main take-off of the continuously run motor turns at 1796 RPM. The main input pulley on the transmission turns at 743 RPM. This speed is further reduced to provide 8 discrete speeds in both a high and low speed setting, from approximately 19 to 560 RPM. The standard operation direction is counterclockwise (CCW), however the transmission allows for the reverse clockwise (CW) operation up to 94 RPM via the forward/reverse selection lever (item 14, Fig. 3a). At some point after the machine was manufactured, the input pulley on the transmission was changed, and therefore the speeds indicated by the speed indicator (item 15, Fig. 3a) do not reflect the actual speed of the spindle. The actual spindle speeds and direction as a function of the position of the three speed selection levers (item 13, Fig. 3a) are given in Tables 4 and 5.

Feedrates and feed directions are set through items 17 and 19, respectively. Item 17 comprises a high-low gear selector, and a rotary lever immediately below selects the speed with settings in threads per inch (TPI). A conversion between the TPI setting and resulting linear movement is provided in Table 6.

Table 2: Lathe spindle and saddle control feature description. Numbered entries correspond to details shown on Fig. 3a.

11	Lubrication sightglass	Displays when the central oiling mechanism is providing enough oil to the top of the transmission.
12	Drive engage lever	Engages the spindle either in low gear by turning the lever towards the saddle (to the right), or in high gear by turning it away from the saddle (left).
13	Speed selection levers	Set of three levers which permit the selection of various speeds. Lever position to approximate speed is displayed on the machine with (15)
14	Forward/reverse selection lever	Permits turning the spindle CCW (forward) or reverse (CW) by turning the lever towards or away from the saddle (right or left), respectively. Changing direction requires the lathe motor turned off.
15	Speed indicator	Dial which shows the position of speed selection levers necessary for an approximate spindle speed.
16	Run/off switch	Latched pushbutton (black) which turns on motor, and a momentary pushbutton (red) to unlatch the motor's run circuit.
17	Feedrate selector	Sets the gear-range for the axial feed rate, position lever towards/away from saddle (right or left) for low and high selections, respectively. Rotary lever selects gear range
18	Manual radial feed wheel	Actuates the tool slide in and out of the workpiece in the R direction. CW direction for $-R$, and CCW for $+R$.
19	Feed direction lever	Changes the rotation direction of the axial feedscrew, such that the saddle will move towards or away from the spindle in-line with the lever position.
20	Manual axial feed wheel	Actuates the saddle along the workpiece. CW for $-z$ and CCW for $+z$.
21	Forward axial feed engage lever	Engages axial feed on the saddle to move in the $+z$ direction. Requires the feed direction lever to be in the 'forward' (left) position.
22	Reverse axial feed engage lever	Engages axial feed on the saddle to move in the $-z$ direction. Requires the feed direction lever to be in the 'reverse' (right) position.

Table 3: Lathe turret control features. Numbered entries correspond to details shown on Fig. 3b.

23	Capstan rotation/lock lever	Not used, may not be in service. Leave in the ‘loose’ position, orthogonal to the z axis.
24	Turret saddle lock	Locks turret saddle in position.
25	Turret feed release lever	Disengages axial feed of turret towards spindle.
26	Capstan release	Allows capstan to be rotated when engaged.
27	Manual turret saddle feed wheel	CW or CCW rotation moves turret saddle away from or towards the spindle, respectively. Turret feed engage lever (28) disables this wheel.
28	Turret feed engage lever	Engages axial feed of turret towards spindle. This has been disabled, but cannot be engaged if the turret is to be rotated.

Table 4: Spindle forward (CCW) speeds and corresponding selection lever positions.

Speed Selection Lever			High/ Low	RPM
Long	Middle	Short		
←	←	→	→	19
			←	24
←	←	←	→	31
			→	38
→	←	→	→	47
			←	59
→	←	←	→	75
			←	94
←	→	→	→	119
			←	145
←	→	←	→	184
			←	231
→	→	→	→	281
			←	353
→	→	←	→	445
			←	560

Table 5: Spindle reverse (CW) speeds and corresponding selection lever positions.

Speed Selection Lever			High/ Low	RPM
Long	Middle	Short		
←	←	→	→	19
			←	24
←	←	←	→	31
			←	39
→	←	→	→	47
			←	59
→	←	←	→	75
			←	94

Table 6: Low spindle speed axial feedrates in inches per minute (IPM) translated from inches per revolution (IPR) of the threads per inch (TPI) setting and spindle speed (RPM).

TPI	IPR	RPM	19	31	47	75	119	184	281	445
20	1.270	IPM	24.13	39.37	59.69	95.25	147.32	233.68	356.87	566.42
40	0.635		12.07	19.69	29.85	47.63	73.66	116.84	178.44	283.21
60	0.423		8.04	13.12	19.90	31.75	49.11	77.89	118.96	188.81
80	0.318		6.03	9.84	14.92	23.81	36.83	58.42	89.22	141.61
120	0.212		4.02	6.56	9.95	15.88	24.55	38.95	59.48	94.40
240	0.106		2.01	3.28	4.97	7.94	12.28	19.47	29.74	47.20
360	0.071		1.34	2.19	3.32	5.29	8.18	12.98	19.83	31.47
480	0.053		1.01	1.64	2.49	3.97	6.14	9.74	14.87	23.60

(a) Front

(b) Top-down

Figure 4: Saddle minor limit: closest to the spindle longitudinally (z direction) and furthest away from the workpiece latitudinally (R direction)

(a) Front

(b) Top-down

Figure 5: Major saddle limit: farthest from the spindle longitudinally (z direction) and closest to the workpiece latitudinally (R direction)

Figure 6: Maximum roller and workpiece diameters. Section view is taken at dashed line indicated in Fig. 4a.

3 Blank design & tooling

In order to avoid making a special mold to generate a blank that satisfies all of the feature requirements, CAPTIN presented a wheel that had a diametrical and length characteristic that satisfying the work envelope described previously. Furthermore, using a wheel casting permitted experimentation with relevant microstructure. From the selection of a blank, the rotary tooling was then devised based on this geometry and a ratio of roller OD to blank ID of 2:3.

3.1 Blank description

While the wheel had the appropriate microstructure, it required machining to create an effective rotary forming blank. Specifically, the wheel face was removed, the mandrel interface faced and the inboard bead was removed. The mandrel interface was faced to simplify the mandrel design and the inboard bead was removed in order to decrease forming loads and bring the overall geometry closer to a cylinder. These operations also served to obfuscate CAPTIN wheel geometry such that the geometry used for the experimental rotary forming could be published. The wheel consisted of a 6 spoke, ~16" wheel with internal part number 300N. A detail of the modified wheel blank is shown in Fig. 7.

Figure 7: Rotary forming blank extracted from a CAPTIN 330 wheel with basic dimensions in mm.

3.2 Rotary tooling

The geometry of the blank provided the inputs necessary to further design the tooling to support it through forming, specifically, the clamping system and mandrel. The complete mandrel and clamping system designed for the 330N blank is depicted in Fig. 8.

Figure 8: Depiction of rotary tooling assembly. The driveshaft connects the main mandrel weldment to the spindle, and is in turn supported by a center engaging the tailstock plate on the front face. The details of the clamp operation are also shown.

The main components of the mandrel consist of a slightly tapered, hollow weldment that is attached to a spindle with a hollow driveshaft. The mandrel's taper was specified to match the taper on the blanks (5°) in the clamp region, which was then blended to a smaller taper (1.5°) intended to ease the release of the blank post-forming. The mandrel weldment is in turn capped by a centering plate which was brought into contact with a spring loaded 'live' centre¹, installed on the tailstock (item 4 in Fig. 2). This centering plate, held in place by a series of bolts, also serves to enclose the mandrel cavity, which contains a wiring harness for 10 type-K TCs that are welded into the surface of the mandrel. Extensions for the TCs are run through the driveshaft and spindle and connected to the wireless DAQ system described in Section ???. All components were constructed of AISI-4320 steel and fitted together with grade 12.9 fasteners, allowing the potential for interchangeable tooling for future experiments.

The method chosen to hold the blank to the mandrel during forming was to use 3 compression clamps which force the inner diameter of the blank onto the outer diameter of the mandrel by pushing on the blank flange. The main functional elements of one of the clamps in the clamping system are shown in the

¹Ritens number 431-17124; #4 Morse taper, bull nose

top right inset of Fig. 8. To engage the clamp, first the clamp bracket is located and fixed to the mandrel with the means of a tapered die pin, passing through the mandrel weldment and the clamp bracket. Clamp element 2 is then fixed perpendicularly to the clamp bracket by a captive shoulder bolt. Afterwards, clamp element 2 is actuated against clamp element 1 with a M16 socket cap screw which passes through the mandrel weldment and threads into the clamp bracket. Tightening this bolt induces clamp element 2 to push the engagement block (element 1) against the face of the blank flange. Fixed to clamp element 2 by socket head cap screws, clamp element 3 is brought into contact with the flange opposite to element 1 as the blank approaches the target forming temperature. Operation of the clamping system requires periodic tightening of the M16 socket cap screws as the blank is heated, with the final ‘hot’ configuration shown in the lower inset of Fig. 8. This design accounts for a large range of thermal expansion and maximizes operator access.

The overall assembly of the mandrel is shown on Dwg. 1 and 14, with a complete bill of materials provided in Table 7, manufactured parts in Table 8 and purchased parts in Table 9.

3.3 Rotary tooling assembly notes

If the current mandrel needs to be removed for modification or service off of the lathe, then The rotary tooling assembly is mainly comprised of bolted flanges. Table 10 provides the necessary torque application for unlubricated grade 12.9 bolts. In the case of a flange or bolt circle, then a ‘star’ type tightening sequence to be used. For example, for a bolt circle with 6 fasteners, the tightening sequence is $1 \rightarrow 4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 5 \rightarrow 3 \rightarrow 6$. At least two tightening passes should be employed, starting with some percentage of the final torques provided in Table 10, with the final tightening pass to match.

In order to install the rotary tooling on the lathe, not all of the fasteners need to be properly torqued. It is much easier to apply the proper torque to each of the bolts when the tooling is in place. Assuming that the tooling is dismantled from the lathe, installation steps are as follows:

1. Move the capstan clear of the mast of the lathe (items 2 and 9, Fig. 2).
2. Rotate the capstan of the lathe counterclockwise by one position (item 9, Fig. 2) such that the steady rest points outward from the lathe.
3. Install the live center and mandrel leveling jig in the appropriate positions on the steady rest (Dwg. 13). Do not tighten the bolts fixing the spigot holding the mandrel leveling jig, but ensure that there is a pin or bolt on the end of the leveling jig to prevent the jig from pulling out of the spigot.
4. Install a 1/2” eyebolt to the centering plate (Dwg. 7), and bolt the plate roughly centered on the mandrel weldment.
5. Install the drive cap (Dwg. 6) using four of the 6 M16 bolts, and install M16 eyebolts in the remaining positions, as per Dwg. 13.
6. Install the driveshaft (Dwg. 14) to the drive cap.
7. Using an appropriate lifting sling choked around the mandrel weldment, lift the entire assembly proximate to the lathe with the overhead crane. Note that the installed position of the lathe does not permit the crane access directly overhead the working axis.
8. Hook the ratcheting tiedown to the 1/2” eyebolt installed on the centering plate, and pull the tooling onto the center. Reposition the crane as necessary such that the mandrel is approximately level.

Table 7: Bill of materials for rotary tooling

Title/Level			Drawing/ Part No.	Appears on	Qty.	Type
L1	L2	L3				
Mandrel Assm.			2 T-1-0	1	1	Assm.
	Mandrel Weld.		3 / T-1-1-0	2	1	Assm.
		Mandrel	4 / T-1-1-1	3	1	Man.
		Mandrel Insert	5 / T-1-1-2	3	1	Man.
	Drive Cap		6 / T-1-3	2	1	Man.
	Centering Plate		7 / T-1-4	2	1	Man.
	M16 Socket Cap		T-1-P1	2	6	Purch.
	M8 Socket Cap		T-1-P2	2	6	Purch.
Clamp Block 1			8 / T-2-1	1	3	Man.
Clamp Block 2 Assm.			9 / T-2-2-0	1	3	Assm.
	Clamp Block 2		10 / T-2-2-1	9	3	Man.
	Clamp Plate		11 / T-2-2-2	9	3	Man.
	M8 Socket Cap		T-2-2-P1	9	6	Purch.
Clamp Block 3 Assm.			†	1	3	Assm.
	Clamp Block 3		12 / T-2-3-1	†	3	Man.
	M8 Shoulder Bolt		T-2-3-P1	†	3	Purch.
Driveshaft Weld.			15 / T-3-0	14	1	Assm.
	Drive Shaft		16 / T-3-1	15	1	Man.
	Non-Drive Side Flange		17 / T-3-2	15	1	Man.
	Drive Side Flange		18 / T-3-3	15	1	Man.
330N Blank			BL-1	1	1	Existing
M12 Socket Cap			T-0-P1	14	6	Purch.
M20 Socket Cap			T-0-P2	14	6	Purch.
M20 Locknut			T-0-P3	14	6	Purch.
2" #6 Taper pin			T-0-P4	†	3	Purch.
M16 Socket Cap			T-0-P5	1	3	Purch.
Spindle Nose			LR-1	14	1	Existing

† Revisions to the clamping system did not extend to assembly drawings. Refer to Fig. 8.

9. Tie off the end of the ratcheting tiedown with the crane still in place.
10. Bring the leveling jig down the face of the steady rest until the leveling feet touch off on the mandrel surface. Once in position, tighten the spigot bolts.
11. Install turn bolts and chain between the leveling jig and driveshaft. Ensure that the chain is choked on the driveshaft, and tighten the turn bolts to level the tooling. Make sure that the tie down on the 1/2" eyebolt has not moved.

Table 8: Rotary tooling parts for manufacture

Title	Drawing/Part No.	Qty.	Raw Material
Mandrel	4 / T-1-1-1	1	∅13.5" x 1" thick x 14.5" AISI 4130 tube
Mandrel Insert	5 / T-1-1-2	1	1/2" AISI 4130 plate
Drive Cap	6 / T-1-3	1	1" AISI 1020/1018 plate
Centering Plate	7 / T-1-4	1	3/8" AISI 1020/1018 plate
Clamp Block 1	8 / T-2-1	3	1-3/4" AISI 4130 plate
Clamp Block 2	10 / T-2-2-1	3	1-3/4" AISI 4130 plate
Clamp Plate	11 / T-2-2-2	3	3/8" AISI 1020/1018 plate
Clamp Block 3	12 / T-2-3-1	3	1-3/4" AISI 1020/1018 plate
Drive Shaft	16 / T-3-1	1	3-1/2" SCH160 A36(min), or AISI 1018/1020 tube
Non-Drive Side Flange	17 / T-3-2	1	1/2" AISI 1020/1018 plate
Drive Side Flange	18 / T-3-3	1	1" AISI 1020/1018 plate

Table 9: Rotary tooling purchased parts

Description	Part No.	Qty.
M12 Socket Cap Screw x 25 mm, McMaster Carr P/N: 91290A616	T-0-P1	6
M20 Socket Cap Screw x 55 mm, McMaster Carr P/N: 91290A851	T-0-P2	6
M20 Locknut, McMaster Carr P/N: 94645A270	T-0-P3	6
2" #6 Taper pin, McMaster Carr P/N: 98390A315	T-0-P4	3
M16 Socket Cap Screw x 55 mm, McMaster Carr P/N: 91290A825	T-0-P5	3
M16 Socket Cap Screw x 35 mm, McMaster Carr P/N: 91290A805	T-1-P1	6
M8 Socket Cap Screw x 20 mm, McMaster Carr P/N: 91290A426	T-2-2-P1	6
M8 Shoulder Bolt x 20 mm, McMaster Carr P/N: 92981A303	T-2-3-P1	3

12. Disengage the lifting sling and move the crane out of the way.
13. Rotate the capstan, and move the tooling assembly to interface with the spindle. The turn bolts may have to be adjusted slightly to get the driveshaft to interface cleanly.
14. Install M20 nuts and bolts to fix the driveshaft to the spindle to approximately 10-20% of the final torque value.
15. Remove leveling jig, turn bolts, chain and tie down. Back off the capstan and remove the centering plate. Remove the M16 eyebolts from the mandrel weldment, and replace with the appropriate M16 bolts.

Table 10: Torque requirements for various rotary tooling bolts

Bolt	Torque (lb·ft)	Bolt	Torque (lb·ft)
M8	30	M16	250
M12	100	M20	300-500

16. Place a dial indicator on the OD of the drive-side flange. Using a brass hammer, minimize circular run-out of the driveshaft. Once minimized, apply tighten the M20 bolts completely.
17. Tighten the M16 bolts connecting the drive cap and mandrel weldment completely.
18. Place the dial indicator on the mandrel weldment, and minimize circular run-out in the same manner as the driveshaft. Note that it is best practice to choose two or three axial positions to measure run-out. Once finalized, tighten the M12 bolts connecting the driveshaft to the drive cap.
19. Remove the eyebolt from the centering plate, and loosely install it on the mandrel weldment. Seat the plate by bringing the center on the capstan into contact. Once in position, tighten the M8 bolts completely.

3.4 Mandrel design

The following sections will describe the main design considerations employed to realize the rotary tooling for the 330N blank, such that other mandrels may be used with the apparatus.

3.4.1 Mandrel regions

This section discusses the various areas of the mandrel with respect to their functions. There are three characteristic lengths depicted in Fig. 9:

1. Clamp engagement length
2. Workpiece engagement length
3. Forming zone length

The length of the clamping section is dependent on the force required to hold the workpiece in place (bolt, clamp element size, etc.) and will be discussed in the following section. The workpiece engagement length is where the workpiece makes contact with the mandrel during preheating and before initial heating. The forming zone is the portion of the mandrel which supports the workpiece during forming. This section discusses how the two latter lengths, the engagement length and the forming length were estimated. The blank does change shape significantly when heated, as depicted in Fig. 9. These dimensions were calculated based on a linear coefficient of thermal expansion, α_l for A356 being $23.5 \mu\text{m}/\text{m}\cdot\text{K}$ at 350°C affecting all dimensions on the ambient workpiece, and $\alpha_{l\text{steel}} = 5.8 \mu\text{m}/\text{m}\cdot\text{K}$ for the carbon steel mandrel OD.

3.4.2 Workpiece engagement length and working diameter

The workpiece engagement length runs from the final seated position of the hot workpiece on the draft of the mandrel at datum point $D = D_h$ in Fig. 9 to the end of the draft angle into the constant diameter portion of the mandrel. The factors affecting the workpiece engagement length are:

- Diametric variance in the workpiece
- Longitudinal variance in the workpiece
- Thermal contraction/expansion of the component

Figure 9: Blank versus mandrel lengths, the datum point $D = D_c$ is on a diameter of 324.08 at room temperature (a), datum point $D = D_h$ is on a diameter of 326.74 at 350°C (b).

Due to the angular draft of the mandrel/workpiece interface, both variance on the diameter and length will decide the final position of the workpiece on the mandrel. If this position is too far up the draft, either the workpiece will buckle during the first forming operation or there will not be enough travel in the clamping system to effectively hold the part during other forming operations. These dimensions must be calculated when the part is hot, and corrected to allow for thermal contraction.

The basic design criteria is that the mandrel draft to constant diameter transition point, point P_m in Fig. 10 be behind the transition point on the outer diameter of the blank, P_b . This is also means that the point P_m is diametrically set on is equal to or smaller than the blank's inner diameter transition point.

3.4.3 Forming length of the mandrel

The forming length of the mandrel is the length of the region with the constant diameter, on which the workpiece will be formed. This corresponds to length 3 in Fig. 9. Starting with a tube of known geometry,

Figure 10: Workpiece engagement detail, point T_m is the transition from the draft to the flat section on the mandrel, and T_b is the transition point on the blank.

the final length of the tube given a wall thickness reduction can be found from Eq. 1.

$$L_f = L_o \left(\frac{t_o (d_i + t_o)}{t_f (d_i + t_f)} \right) \quad (1)$$

In actuality, the mandrel should be longer than this minimum length in order to account for unforeseen dimensional variance in the blank, deflection during mounting and thermal effects which may cause the form to extend further from the datum than anticipated.

3.4.4 Mandrel wall thickness and fastener requirements

The wall thickness of the mandrel must be such that the loads imparted on it result in small compliance for both the clamping loads and forming loads. As there will be structure to support the clamp loads in the form of the tailstock end cap, and that the forming loads are foreseen to be in excess of the clamping loads, the mandrel thickness should be driven by the forming loads, minimizing both deflection and weight for the forming configuration required. This section details how forming loads were estimated, deflection calculated, and fastener design factors.

Rolling analogy Using a rolling analogy, the normal/radial force acting on the mandrel surface can be estimated using a plane strain slab method according to the diagram in Fig. 11a to arrive at a point load acting radially on the mandrel. The force P_r acts on the flow forming roller of radius R_r to reduce the material initially t_o thick set on the mandrel of radius R_m to t_f thick over an projected interface L wide.

The actual length of contact, l , can be found from the following, where R can be either R_m or R_r :

$$l^2 = L^2 + \left(\frac{t_o - t_f}{2} \right)^2 \quad (2)$$

$$L^2 = R^2 - \left(R - \frac{t_o - t_f}{2} \right)^2 \quad (3)$$

$$l = \sqrt{R(t_o - t_f)} \quad (4)$$

Setting $t = \frac{t_o + t_f}{2}$, the pressure exerted by the roller on the material is estimated by [1]:

$$P_r = \frac{t}{\mu l} \left(\exp \frac{\mu l}{t} - 1 \right) (\sigma_y - \sigma_t) \quad (5)$$

Figure 11: Rolling and extrusion analogies of rotary forming.

where μ is the coefficient of friction, σ_y is the flow stress of the material and σ_t is the back tension applied to the material during standard rolling. In applying this equation to flow forming, back tension is actually compressive, arising from undeformed material acting on the forming zone. The maximum σ_t can be in this case is the flow stress of the material resulting in:

$$P_r = 2 \frac{t}{\mu l} \left(\exp \frac{\mu l}{t} - 1 \right) \sigma_y \quad (6)$$

The friction factor μ was estimated by from multiplying the ratio of static friction coefficients of steel on steel (0.8) versus aluminum on steel (0.61) times the dynamic friction factor found for rolling of steel (0.075). The pressure P_r was estimated to be transferred to the mandrel through the material over an area estimated as L times half of the width of the roller, to arrive at an estimated point load due to the rolling 'component' of the deformation, F_r .

Extrusion analogy To arrive at an estimate of the point load acting axially on the workpiece, then an extrusion analogy is useful as shown in Fig. 11b. Here, the material changes from thickness t_o to t_f over a circumferential contact on the mandrel side of θ_m , contacting the workpiece between points p_1 and p_2 axially.

The circumferential contact length as measured on the mandrel (θ_m) can be calculated as:

$$\theta_m = \arctan \frac{X}{Y} \quad (7)$$

where X and Y are given by:

$$X = \frac{(R_m + t_f + R_r)^2 - R_r^2 + (R_m + t_o)}{2(R_m + t_f + R_r)} \quad (8)$$

$$Y = \sqrt{(R_m + t_o)^2 - X^2} \quad (9)$$

$$(10)$$

The circumferential contact length as measured on the roller (θ_r) can be calculated as:

$$\theta_r = \arctan \frac{Y}{(R_m + t_f + R_r) - X} \quad (11)$$

The original cross-sectional thickness of the workpiece directly under the influence of the roller is given by:

$$A_o = \frac{\theta_m}{2} \left((R_m + t_o)^2 - R_m^2 \right) \quad (12)$$

and the change in cross-section through thickness area (ΔA) can be expressed as:

$$\Delta A = \frac{\theta_m}{2} (R_m + t_o)^2 - \left((R_m + t_f + R_r) - X \right) \frac{Y}{2} + \frac{\theta_r}{2} R_r^2 - \frac{XY}{2} \quad (13)$$

The strain that is therefore imparted to the material is:

$$\varepsilon = \ln \frac{A_o}{A_o - \Delta A} \quad (14)$$

Assuming that the material is deforming at σ_y , then an estimate [2] of the force required to deform the material, F_e , is as follows:

$$F_e = \sigma_y(\mu + Q\varepsilon)A_o \quad (15)$$

where μ is a friction factor (estimated at 0.8) and Q (~ 1.2) is an empirical factor to account for inhomogeneous deformation. Note that F_e must be counteracted by an appropriate clamping system, such that the force delivered by the clamp mechanism should be at least 2-3 times F_e .

Deflection Deflection should be minimized as much as possible. The current mandrel employed for the 330N-type blank has been designed to deflect less than 0.02 mm across the entire length, from the spindle to the tailstock, based on a radial (F_r) forming load of 12-13 kN. The deflection anywhere along the length of the mandrel can be calculated from the bending moment such that:

$$\frac{d^2y}{dx^2} = \frac{M}{EI} \quad (16)$$

and the deflection:

$$y = \iint \left(\frac{M}{EI} dx \right) dx \quad (17)$$

where M is the bending moment, E the modulus of elasticity, I is the area moment of inertia of the mandrel cross section at x , y is the deflection. As the mandrel has a complicated cross-section, with different moments of inertia, in order to solve for deflection numerical evaluation is recommended [3].

Fasteners The current design of the mandrel is modular with different segments bolting together. This design enables experimental flexibility, potential tooling savings by not having to use a large piece of billet and eliminates potential weld failures which may stem from higher-carbon steel. As a result, bolts must be selected such that an acceptable factor of safety (FOS) is maintained.

There are three principal loads placed on the bolts:

1. Bolt preload (tensile).
2. Reaction force from extrusion-type loading F_e (shear).
3. Reaction force from rolling-type loading F_r (shear).

The bolt preload will be uniform, the extrusion-type loading will be dictated by process parameters as will the rolling-type loading. However, both of these latter loads will be magnified the further away from the axis of revolution of the mandrel they are located. Therefore, bolt heads located on the OD of the mandrel's forming region will be under the greatest load.

The criteria that has been employed to ensure that appropriate fasteners are used is to ensure that every bolt which communicates the spindle to the forming zone is capable of withstanding the stall torque of the lathe, with a factor of safety. The premise is that if anything untoward occurs during a forming experiment, tooling integrity is ensured while the belts slip. In other words, regardless of the values of F_r and F_e , tooling integrity is maintained.

Torque-to-stall, J_s in kN·m is calculated by:

$$J_s = \frac{3.3 \times 10^5 P}{2S\pi(0.112984)} \quad (18)$$

where P is the lathe motor power rating in HP and S is speed in RPM. The shear force acting on a single fastener can therefore be expressed as:

$$F_{\tau} = \frac{6.6 \times 10^5 P}{2DN_f S \pi (0.112984)} \quad (19)$$

where N_f fastener heads are set on diameter D . For example, the lathe's 30 HP motor turning at a speed of 100 RPM will exert 13.9 kN on each of 6 bolt heads located on the surface of a mandrel with 336 mm OD. The relationship of both J_s and total F_{τ} (i.e. $N_f = 1$) versus speed for this scenario is given in Fig. 12. The suggested operating window is indicated by dotted lines in this figure, where both an appreciable amount of torque is available and the force exerted by an untoward forming event resulting in stalling is minimized. Furthermore, combining a this calculated estimate of F_{τ} (Eq. 19) with F_r (derived from Eq. 6) and F_e (Eq. 15) to determine if the lathe is capable of a particular forming operation.

Figure 12: Lathe torque output versus speed and total force which must be exerted on the surface of the mandrel ($D = 168$ mm) to stall.

Fastener preload, the amount of tension that must be placed on the fastener prior to service usually ranges between 50-90% of σ_y . The force placed on the head of the fastener (F_p) is this fraction of yield stress divided by bolt cross-sectional area. With F_{τ} and F_p , factors of safety can be calculated considering the fastened joint either in a bearing (FOS_b) or a friction (FOS_f) context. Both factors should be above at least two.

These factors of safety require calculating an equivalent stress corresponding to both preload and stall force. Note that in this calculation, the only forces acting on the bolt are F_p and F_{τ} over the same cross-sectional area. Therefore, employing a Von Mises criterion:

$$F_{eq} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{3} \left((F_1 - F_2)^2 + F_1^2 + F_2^2 \right)} \quad (20)$$

where F_1 and F_2 are forces correspond to the first and second principal stresses, calculated by:

$$F_1 = \frac{F_p + \sqrt{F_p^2 - 4F_\tau^2}}{2} \quad (21)$$

$$F_2 = \frac{F_p - \sqrt{F_p^2 - 4F_\tau^2}}{2} \quad (22)$$

with FOS_b and FOS_f calculated as:

$$FOS_b = \frac{F_{eq}}{F_p} \quad (23)$$

$$FOS_f = \frac{F_p \mu}{F_\tau} \quad (24)$$

where μ is a friction factor ranging between 0.2 and 0.8 for lubricated versus unlubricated steel-on-steel interfaces. Note that FOS_f is the most conservative.

With the current 330N mandrel, high degrees of FOS are achieved by using high-grade bolts (i.e. a higher F_p is possible) and precluding forming operations at speeds less than 150 RPM.

Note that this apparatus is designed to operated at elevated temperatures which will affect the temper of both base mandrel and fastener material. It is not known what the service life of the bolts that were used. It is suggested that bolts with lower factors of safety should be replaced if any stall event takes place, and fasteners experiencing the greatest exposure to temperature be replaced on a regular basis.

3.5 Roller and toolstand

The tool stand received with the lathe consisted of three main components: a tool holder mounted on a pivot block, which in turn was fixed to a riser communicating with the saddle. This tool stand was originally intended to hold up to four turning tools orthogonal to the workpiece by a locking pin mechanism located in the pivot block. This mechanism was modified such that the tool holder could be fixed at arbitrary angles from the R direction by the installation of a jam nut assembly, as shown in Fig. 13. A AISI-8620 roller with a diameter of 120 mm and a nose radius of 10 mm was set on an axle with a thrust bearing assembly packed with high temperature grease². The AISI-4320 axle was held in place by a pinch-bolt on a bar held captive by AISI-1035 lateral bracing members, which was then mated to the tool holder. The tool stand angle was fixed at 15° from the R direction for all experiments. The temperature of the roller remained below that of the mandrel, as it was only directly heated by contact with the workpiece during the course of forming.

The overall assembly is shown in Dwg. 19, the complete BOM is shown in Table 11, manufactured parts are shown in Table 12 and purchased parts in Table 13.

3.5.1 Modifying toolstand orientation

In order to change the current 15° orientation of the toolstand, the toolstand will have to be partially disassembled, as shown in Fig. 14. Start by removing the 1-1/8" nut at the top of the toolstand (1). Next,

²Dow Corning Molykote BR2 Plus

Figure 13: Roller and tool stand detail.

Table 11: Bill of materials for roller assembly

Title/Level			Drawing/ Part No.	Appears on	Qty.	Type
L1	L2	L3				
Roller Arm Assembly			20 / R-1-0	19	1	Assm.
	Roller Assembly		21 / R-1-1-0	20	1	Assm.
		Roller Body	22 / R-1-1-1	21	1	Man.
		Tapered Roller Bearing	23 / R-1-1-P1	21	2	Purch.
		Low Rise Seal	24 / R-1-1-P2	21	2	Purch.
	Roller Arm Support		25 / R-1-2	20	1	Man.
	Outboard Spacer		26 / R-1-3	20	1	Man.
	Roller Shaft		27 / R-1-4	20	1	Man.
	Lock Washer		28 / R-1-P1	20	1	Purch.
	Lock Nut		29 / R-1-P2	20	1	Purch.
	M16 Socket Cap		R-1-P3	20	1	Purch.
Rear Brace			30 / R-2	19	1	Man.
Rear Brace			31 / R-3	19	1	Man.
Tool Holder Block			LR-2	19	1	Existing

Table 12: Roller assembly parts for manufacture

Title	Drawing/Part No.	Qty.	Raw Material
Roller Body	22 / R-1-1-1	1	∅10" x 1.75" 8620 Impacto
Roller Support Arm	25 / R-1-2	1	1" x 3" AISI 4140/4130 flat bar
Outboard Spacer	26 / R-1-3	1	∅2.5" 1/2" 4140/4130 round
Roller Shaft	27 / R-1-4	1	∅2.5" x 4" 4140/4130 round
Rear Brace	30 / R-2	1	1" x 2.5" AISI 1020/1035 CRS flat bar
Front Brace	31 / R-3	1	1" x 2.5" AISI 1020/1035 CRS flat bar

Table 13: Roller assembly purchased parts

Description	Drawing/Part No.	Qty.
SKF Tapered Roller Bearing, ∅25/47, 32005 X/Q	23 / R-1-1-P1	2
SKF Low Rise Radial Shaft Seal, G 38x48x4	24 / R-1-1-P2	2
SKF Lock Washer, MB5	28 / R-1-P1	1
SKF Lock Nut, KM5	29 / R-1-P2	1
M16 Socket Cap Screw x 55 mm, McMaster Carr P/N: 91290A825	R-1-P3	1

Figure 14: Toolstand orientation adjustment

remove the toolstand crown and washer by removing the 6 socket cap screws at the top of the toolstand (2). This will expose a second interior nut (3), which should be loosened a few turns to release pressure on the jam nut assembly. Tapping the jam blocks (4) underneath the interior jam nut should release them enough to allow the toolstand to pivot. In the case in which they are seized, remove one or both of the pin covers (5) and tap on the blocks laterally with a soft metal drift.

If the jam blocks do not become dislodged with a drift, remove the 1-1/8" threaded rod completely from the assembly, exposing the ID of the jam blocks. The top jam block can be extracted by using a puller installed in the cross-drilled holes. Upon reassembly, reverse the disassembly process. Lubricate the threaded shaft and nuts with a lightweight machine oil and apply at least 500 ft-lbs to each of the 1-1/8" nuts. Rust inhibitor may be applied to the jam blocks, but do not lubricate the bearing surfaces.

4 Heating system

In order to create a flexible heating system which could be scaled as needed, propane heating was selected as the principal heating method. The heating system consisted of a bank of four propane torch assemblies that are installed on the mast of the lathe. The torches are held in a framework that permits adjustment of the various torch positions and their distances away from the blank (Fig. 15). The total heat output of

Figure 15: Propane heating system.

the torch tips employed³ was rated at 82 kW. Propane is supplied through an automotive-type, nominally closed solenoid and regulator at 34.5 kPa, and is distributed to the torches with a manifold containing individual ball valves. The control solenoid permitted rapid cycling of the propane supply, but the torches were lit manually. The final position of the torches was arrived at by making small adjustments until the blank heated rapidly and uniformly.

The overall assembly of the heating system is shown on Dwg. 32, with a complete bill of materials provided in Table 14, manufactured parts in Table 15 and purchased parts in Table 16.

³Rothenberger/Exact model 3135

Table 14: Bill of materials for heating system assembly

Title/Level		Drawing/ Part No.	Appears on	Qty.	Type	
L1	L2	L3				
Torch Holder	Torch		33 / H-1-0	32	1	Assm.
			34 / H-1-1-0	33	4	Assm.
		1/4" NPT Nipple	35 / H-1-1-P1	34	1	Purch
		Male M20 to 1/4" F-NPT Adapter	H-1-1-P2	34	1	Purch.
		3119 Exact Tip [†]	H-1-1-P3	21	1	Purch.
		1/4" F-NPT Coupler	H-1-1-P4	34	1	Purch
		1/4" M-NPT to LH Flare Adapter	H-1-1-P5	34	1	Purch
		Support Arm [‡]	36 / H-1-2	33	1	Man.
	Mount Plate	37 / H-1-3	33	1	Man.	
	Binding Plate	38 / H-1-4	33	1	Man.	
	3 – 1/4" U bolt	39 / H-1-P1	33	2	Purch.	
	3/8" Nut	H-1-P2	33	6	Purch.	
	3/8" x 1" Bolt	H-1-P3	33	2	Purch.	
	3/8" Washer	H-1-P4	33	2	Purch.	
	1/4" Washer	H-1-P5	33	8	Purch.	
	1/4" x 1-1/8" Bolt	H-1-P6	33	5	Purch.	
	1/4" Nut	H-1-P7	33	5	Purch.	
	Distributor		40 / H-2-0	32	1	Assm.
		Distributor Body	41 / H-2-1	40	1	Man.
		Distributor Mount Plate	42 / H-2-2	40	1	Man.
Regulator Support		43 / H-2-3	40	1	Man.	
1/4" NPT Hex Barb		44 / H-2-P1	40	5	Purch.	
1" M-NPT to 1/4" F-NPT Hex Bushing		45 / H-2-P2	40	1	Purch.	
3 – 1/4" U bolt		39 / H-2-P3	40	2	Purch.	
3/8" Nut		H-2-P4	40	4	Purch.	
2" Square U bolt		46 / H-2-P5	40	2	Purch.	
SV-S121 Solenoid Valve		H-2-P6	40	1	Purch.	
67CH-743 0-30 psi Regulator		H-2-P7	40	1	Purch.	

L1	Title/Level		Drawing/ Part No.	Appears on	Qty.	Type
	L2	L3				
	1/4" NPT Tee		47 / H-2-P8	40	1	Purch.
	General Service Pressure Gauge		48 / H-2-P9	40	1	Purch.
	1 - 1/2" x 1/4" NPT Nipple		49 / H-2-P10	40	3	Purch.
	1/4" F-NPT Panel Mount		50 / H-2-P11	40	1	Purch.
	Short Handle 1/4" F-NPT Valve		H-2-P12	40	4	Purch.
	1/4" M-NPT to LH Flare Adapter		H-2-P13	40	4	Purch.
Hose Support			51 / H-3-0	32	1	Assm.
	Hose Bracket		52 / H-3-1	51	1	Man.
	9/16" Hose Clamp		53 / H-3-P1	51	4	Purch.
	8-32 x 3/8" Bolt		H-3-P2	51	4	Purch.
60" SAE 1/2" Female Flare End Hose			H-0-P1	32	4	Purch.
72" 1/4" x POL Whip			H-0-P2	32	1	Purch.
20/40 lb POL Fitted Propane Tank			H-0-P3	32	1	Purch.

[†]Note that this tip was initially employed, and then changed to the larger capacity 3135 model. Refer to Fig. 15b.

[‡]Revisions to the support arm assembly did not extend to drawings. Refer to Fig. 15b.

Table 15: Heating system parts for manufacture

Title	Part/Drawing No.	Qty.	Raw Material
Support Arm	36 / H-1-2	1	3"x2"x3/16" Mild Steel \angle x 12"
Mount Plate	37 / H-1-3	1	2"x2"x3/16" Mild Steel \angle x 9-7/8"
Binding Plate	38 / H-1-4	1	2"x1/8" Mild Steel Flat Bar x 7"
Distributor Body	41 / H-2-1	1	2"x2" Cold Rolled Steel Bar x 9-1/4"
Distributor Mount Plate	42 / H-2-2	2	2-1/2"x1/8" Mild Steel Flat Bar x 3-3/4"
Regulator Support	43 / H-2-3	1	2"x1/8" Mild Steel Flat Bar x 18-1/2" & 2"x2"x1/8" Mild Steel \angle x 2"
Hose Bracket	52 / H-3-1	1	2-1/2"x3/16" Mild Steel Flat Bar x 4-1/2" & 1"x1"x3/16" Mild Steel \angle x 18"

Table 16: Heating system purchased parts

Description	Local Part No.	Qty.	Supplier
1/4" NPT Nipple	35 / H-1-1-P1	4	McMaster Carr
Male M20 to 1/4" F-NPT Adapter	H-1-1-P2	4	Aztec
3119 Exact Tip	H-1-1-P3	4	Aztec
1/4" F-NPT Coupler	H-1-1-P4	4	Aztec
3 – 1/4" U bolt	39 / H-1-P1 & H-2-P3	4	McMaster Carr
3/8" Nut 93827A225	H-1-P2 & H-2-P4	10	McMaster Carr
3/8" x 1" Bolt 91251A624	H-1-P3	2	McMaster Carr
3/8" Washer 98029A031	H-1-P4	2	McMaster Carr
1/4" Washer 98029A027	H-1-P5	8	McMaster Carr
1/4" x 1-1/8" Bolt 91251A560	H-1-P6	5	McMaster Carr
1/4" Nut 93827A211	H-1-P7	5	McMaster Carr
1/4" NPT Hex Barb	44 / H-2-P1	5	McMaster Carr
1" M-NPT to 1/4" F-NPT Hex Bushing	45 / H-2-P2	1	McMaster Carr
2" Square U bolt	46 / H-2-P5	2	McMaster Carr
SV-S121 Solenoid Valve	H-2-P6	1	Aztec
67CH-743 0-30 psi Regulator	H-2-P7	1	Aztec
1/4" NPT Tee	47 / H-2-P8	1	McMaster Carr
General Service Pressure Gauge	48 / H-2-P9	1	McMaster Carr
1 – 1/2" x 1/4" NPT Nipple	49 / H-2-P10	3	McMaster Carr
1/4" F-NPT Panel Mount	50 / H-2-P11	1	McMaster Carr
Short Handle 1/4" F-NPT Valve	H-2-P12	4	Aztec
1/4" M-NPT to LH Flare	H-2-P13 & H-1-1-P5	8	Aztec
9/16" Hose Clamp	53 / H-3-P1	4	McMaster Carr
8-32 x 3/8" Bolt 93075A192	H-3-P2	4	McMaster Carr
60" SAE 1/2" Female Flare End Hose	H-0-P1	4	Aztec
72" 1/4" x POL Whip	H-0-P2	1	Aztec
20/40 lb POL Fitted Propane Tank	H-0-P3	1	Superior

5 Instrumentation and Rotary DAQ

5.1 Mandrel thermocouple installation

The overall assembly is shown in Dwg. 54, the complete BOM is shown in Table 17, manufactured parts are shown in Table 18 and purchased parts in Table 19.

Table 17: Bill of materials for mandrel thermocouple installation

Title/Level			Drawing/ Part No.	Appears on	Qty.	Type
L1	L2	L3				
Mandrel TC Instal- lation			54 / T-4-0	54	1	Assm.
	Mandrel TC Mod. TC Harness		55 / T-4-1	55	1	Man.
		Left TC Harness Bracket	56 / T-4-2-0	54	1	Assm.
		Right TC Harness Bracket	57 / T-4-2-1	56	1	Man.
		1/4-20 x 5/8" Hex Standoff	58 / T-4-2-2	56	1	Man.
		1/4-20 x 1" Cap Bolt	T-4-2-P1	56	2	Purch.
		1/4-20 x 6-25/32" Threaded rod	T-4-2-P2	56	2	Purch.
		TC Bundle (10 Pieces)	T-4-2-P3	56	1	Purch.
		#4-40 x 6-25/32" Threaded Rod	T-4-2-P4	56	1	Purch.
		1/4-20 x 7/32" Nut	T-4-2-P5	56	2	Purch.
		#4-40 x 3/32" Nut	T-4-2-P6	56	2	Purch.
	M8 x 25 Socket Head Cap Bolt		T-4-2-P7	56	2	Purch.
	M8 x 8 Nut		T-4-P1	54	2	Purch.
			T-4-P2	54	2	Purch.

5.2 Rotary DAQ

In order to monitor instrumentation installed on the rotating tooling and workpieces, a ruggedized DAQ solution was necessary that could be operated remotely (Fig. 16). To meet these needs, a DAQ system was designed to be directly connected to the spindle and spin with the workpiece. All of the DAQ components are set on a freely rotating shaft mounted to a coupler that directly communicates with the lathe spindle. Clockwise and counterclockwise angular acceleration/deceleration of the DAQ is dampened with a series of four opposed gas springs, acting about the shaft between the DAQ components and the coupler.

The electrical components of the system consist of a USB DAQ board⁴ which is connected to a solid state, small form factor wireless computer. Power for both the DAQ board and the computer is delivered

⁴Measurement Computing 2416

Table 18: Manufactured parts for TC installation

Title	Part/Drawing No.	Qty.	Raw Material
Left TC Harness Bracket	57 / T-4-2-1	1	1-3/16" x 6-3/16" 12 ga. sheet steel
Right TC Harness Bracket	58 / T-4-2-2	1	1-3/16" x 6-3/16" 12 ga. sheet steel

Table 19: Purchased TC installation parts

Description	Local Part No.	Qty.	Supplier
1/4-20 x 5/8" Hex Standoff	T-4-2-P1	2	As req.
1/4-20 x 1" Cap Bolt	T-4-2-P2	2	As req.
1/4-20 x 6-25/32" Threaded rod	T-4-2-P3	1	As req.
TC Bundle (10 Pieces)	T-4-2-P4	1	Supplied
#4-40 x 6-25/32" Threaded Rod	T-4-2-P5	1	As req.
1/4-20 x 7/32" Nut	T-4-2-P6	2	As req.
#4-40 x 3/32" Nut	T-4-2-P7	2	As req.
M8 x 25 Socket Head Cap Bolt	T-4-P1	2	As req.
M8 x 8 Nut	T-4-P2	2	As req.

by 12 D-cell NiMH rechargeable batteries. As needed, the computer running logging software⁵ is operated remotely to monitor TCs in the mandrel (Fig. 8) and blank via a Virtual Network Control (VNC) connection during forming operations.

The overall assembly is shown in Dwg. 59, the complete BOM is shown in Table 20, purchased parts in Table 21 and manufactured parts are shown in Table 22. Connections are listed in Table 23.

⁵National Instruments LabVIEW

Figure 16: Rotary DAQ detail.

Table 20: Bill of materials for rotary DAQ assembly

L1	Title/Level		Drawing/ Part No.	Appears on	Qty.	Type
	L2	L3				
	USB 2416		D-0-E	59 / D-0	1	Exist.
	DAQ Shaft		93 / D-0-P1	59	1	Purch./Mod.
	Gas Spring Assembly		61 / D-0-P2-0	59	4	Purch.
		15 lb Gas Spring	D-0-P2-P1	61	1	Purch.
		Gas Spring Knuckle	62 / D-0-P2-P2	61	1	Purch.
	Coupler Assembly		63 / D-1-0	59	1	Assm.
		Coupler Body	64 / D-1-1	63	1	Man.
		Outer Bushing Plate	65 / D-1-2	63	1	Man.
		Coupler Nut	66 / D-1-3	63	1	Man.
		3/4" Shaft Collar	D-1-P1	63	1	Purch.
		Sleeve Bushing	D-1-P2	63	1	Purch.
		Gas Spring Joint	D-1-P3	63	4	Purch.
		5/16"-18 Nut	D-1-P4	63	4	Purch.
		1/4"-20 x 9/16" Cap	D-1-P5	63	4	Purch.
		Screw				
		Flange Bushing	70 / D-1-P6	63	1	Purch.
	DAQ Support Assembly		71 / D-2-0	59	1	Assm.
		DAQ Support Plate As- sembly	72 / D-2-1-0	71	2	Assm.
		DAQ Support Plate	73 / D-2-1-1	72	1	Man.
		1/4"-20 x 3/4" Flat SHCS	D-2-1-P1	72	4	Purch.
		1/4"-20 Locknut	D-2-1-P2	72	2	Purch.
		1/4" EPDM Washer	D-2-1-P3	72	6	Purch.
		1/4"-20 x 9/16" Cap	D-2-1-P4	72	4	Purch.
		Screw				
		Take-off Plate	74 / D-2-2	71	1	Man.
		Flanged Shaft Collar	75 / D-2-P1	71	1	Purch.
		3/16" x 3/16" x 1" Key- stock	D-2-P2	71	1	Purch.
		5/16"-18 Nut	D-2-P3	71	4	Purch.
		Gas Spring Joint	D-2-P4	71	4	Purch.

L1	Title/Level		Drawing/ Part No.	Appears on	Qty.	Type
	L2	L3				
Power Manager	1/4"-20 x 9/16" Cap Screw		D-2-1-P5	72	3	Purch.
	1/4"-20 Locknut		D-2-P6	71	4	Purch.
	Power Control Circuit		76 / D-3-0	59	1	Assm.
	1/4" Steel Washer		77 / D-3-EL1 & 78 / D-3-EL1	76	1	Man.
	1/4" EPDM Washer		D-3-P1	76	2	Purch.
	1/4"-20 x 2-1/2" Cap Screw		D-3-P2	76	2	Purch.
	1/4"-20 x 9/16" Cap Screw		D-3-P3	76	1	Purch.
	Generic Red Binding Post		D-3-P4	76	1	Purch.
	2.5 mm DC Jack		D-3-P5	76	1	Purch.
	T 1-3/4 LED Clip		79 / D-3-P6	76	3	Purch.
	T 1-3/4 LED Retainer		D-3-P7	76	4	Purch.
	Red 5mm T 1-3/4 LED		D-3-P8	76	4	Purch.
	Amber 5mm T 1-3/4 LED		D-3-P9	76	1	Purch.
	Green 5mm T 1-3/4 LED		D-3-P10	76	1	Purch.
	DPDT Locking Switch		D-3-P11	76	2	Purch.
	DPDT Locking Switch		80 / D-3-P12	76	1	Purch.
	Crush Washer		D-3-P13	76	1	Purch.
	DPDT Locking Switch Nut		D-3-P14	76	2	Purch.
	#6-32 x 1" Nylon Stand-off		D-3-P15	76	3	Purch.
	Binding Post Nut		D-3-P16	76	2	Purch.
	DC Jack Washer		79 / D-3-P17	76	3	Purch.
DC Jack Nut		79 / D-3-P18	76	3	Purch.	
Hammond 1411J Base		81 / D-3-P19	76	1	Purch./Mod.	
Hammond 1411J Cover		82 / D-3-P20	76	1	Purch./Mod.	
#6 Self-tapping Machine Screw		D-3-P21	76	4	Purch.	

L1	Title/Level		Drawing/ Part No.	Appears on	Qty.	Type
	L2	L3				
	Generic Black Binding Post		D-3-P22	76	1	Purch.
Battery Assm			83 / D-4-0	59	1	Assm.
	Battery Mount		84 / D-4-1	83	2	Man.
	D-Cell Assembly		85 / D-4-P1-0	83	6	Assm.
		BH2DL Battery Holder	86 / D-4-P1-P1	85	1	Purch.
		D-Cell Battery	87 / D-4-P1-P2	85	2	Purch.
		#5 Tooth Lock Washer	D-4-P1-P3	85	2	Purch.
		#5-40 x 3/8" Machine Screw	D-4-P1-P4	85	2	Purch.
		#5-40 Locknut	D-4-P1-P5	85	2	Purch.
	1/4"-20 Locknut	D-4-P2		83	8	Purch.
CPU Assm			88 / D-5-0	59	1	Assm.
	CPU Backer		89 / D-5-1	88	1	Man.
	Serener GS-L05		D-5-P1	88	1	Purch.
	1/4"-20 x 3/4" Flat SHCS		D-5-P2	88	4	Purch.
	Sleeve Bushing		?? / D-1-P2	88	1	Purch.
	1/4" EPDM Washer		D-5-P4	88	10	Purch.
	1/4"-20 x 1" Flange Hex Cap Screw		D-5-P5	88	6	Purch.
	1/4"-20 Locknut	D-5-P6		88	6	Purch.
	High-Damp Grommet	D-5-P7		88	6	Purch.
DAQ Retainer			90 / D-6-0	59	1	Assm.
	DAQ Holder Plate		91 / D-6-1	90	1	Man.
	DAQ Holder Pad		92 / D-6-2	90	1	Man.
	1/4"-20 Locknut	D-6-P1		90	2	Purch.
2.5 mm DC Plug			D-0-P1	59	4	Purch.
3/4" Cable Tie Post			D-0-P2	59	10	Purch.
2.1 mm DC Plug			D-0-P3	59	1	Purch.

Table 21: Purchased rotary DAQ parts

Description	Local Part No.	Qty.	Supplier	PN
DAQ Shaft	93 / D-0-P1	1	McMaster Carr	1497K956 [†]
15 lb Gas Spring	D-0-P2-P1	4	McMaster Carr	9416K14
Gas Spring Knuckle	62 / D-0-P2-P2	8	McMaster Carr	9416K86
3/4" Shaft Collar	67 / D-1-P1	1	McMaster Carr	6435K16
Sleeve Bushing	?? / D-1-P2	2	McMaster Carr	6126K49
Gas Spring Joint	?? / D-1-P3	8	McMaster Carr	9512K73
5/16"-18 Nut	D-1-P4/D-2-P3	8	McMaster Carr	93827A219
Flange Bushing	70 / D-1-P6	1	McMaster Carr	6389K437
1/4"-20 x 9/16" Cap Screw	D-1-P5/D-2-1-P4/D-2-P5/D-3-P4	14	McMaster Carr	92620A539
1/4"-20 x 3/4" Flat SHCS	D-2-1-P1/D-5-P2	12	McMaster Carr	91253A540
1/4"-20 Locknut	D-2-1-P2/D-2-P6/D-3-P5/D-4-P2/D-5-P6	26	McMaster Carr	97135A210
1/4" EPDM Washer	D-2-1-P3/D-5-P4/D-3-P2	22	McMaster Carr	90130A029
Flanged Shaft Collar	75 / D-2-P1	1	McMaster Carr	9684T3
3/16" x 3/16" x 1" Keystock	D-2-P2	1	McMaster Carr	98535A140 [‡]
Zener Diode 5.6V 0.5W	77 / D-3-EL1	1	Digikey	1N5232BFSCT-ND
5V, 2A DC-DC Converter	77 / D-3-EL1	1	Digikey	445-2435-ND
LM324 Quad Op-amp	77 / D-3-EL1	1	Digikey	LM324ANFS-FD
1/4" Steel Washer	D-3-P1	2	McMaster Carr	91090A105
1/4"-20 x 2-1/2" Cap Screw	D-2-P7/D-3-P3	2	McMaster Carr	Purch.
Generic Red Binding Post	D-3-P5	1	Digikey	N/A
Switchcraft 712a 2.5 mm DC Jack	79 / D-3-P6	3	Newark	37F2993
T 1-3/4 LED Clip	D-3-P7	4	Digikey	N/A
T 1-3/4 LED Retainer	D-3-P8	4	Digikey	N/A
Red 5mm T 1-3/4 LED 2cd, 20°	D-3-P9	1	Digikey	N/A
Amber 5mm T 1-3/4 LED	D-3-P10	1	Newark	MCL053SBC
Green 5mm T 1-3/4 LED	D-3-P11	2	Digikey	5161337-ND
DPDT Locking Switch	80 / D-3-P12	1	Digikey	360-1849-ND
DPDT Locking Switch Crush Washer	D-3-P13	1	Digikey	360-1849-ND
DPDT Locking Switch Nut	D-3-P14	1	Digikey	360-1849-ND
#6-32 x 1" Nylon Standoff	D-3-P15	3	Digikey	N/A
Binding Post Nut	D-3-P16	2	Digikey	N/A
DC Jack Washer	79 / D-3-P17	3	Newark	37F2993

Description	Local Part No.	Qty.	Supplier	PN
DC Jack Nut	79 / D-3-P18	3	Newark	37F2993
Hammond 1411J Base	81 / D-3-P19	1	WESCO	1411J*
Hammond 1411J Cover	82 / D-3-P20	1	WESCO	1411J*
#6 Self-tapping Machine Screw	D-3-P21	4	WESCO	1411J
Generic Black Binding Post	D-3-P22	1	Digikey	N/A
BH2DL Battery Holder	86 / D-4-P1-P1	6	Digikey	BH2DL-ND
D-Cell Battery	87 / D-4-P1-P2	12	Battery World	DSE-SI-NH-D9000-C-V07A
#5 Tooth Lock Washer	D-4-P1-P3	12	McMaster Carr	91114A006
#5-40 x 3/8" Machine Screw	D-4-P1-P4	12	McMaster Carr	90283A126
#5-40 Locknut	D-4-P1-P5	12	McMaster Carr	90633A006
Serener GS-L05	D-5-P1	1	Logic Supply	Serener GS-L05
1/4"-20 x 1" Flange Hex Cap Screw	D-5-P5	6	McMaster Carr	92316A542
High-Damp Grommet	D-5-P7	6	McMaster Carr	9311K137
Switchcraft 760 2.5 mm DC Plug	93 / D-0-P1	4	Newark	37F2995
3/4" Cable Tie Post	D-0-P2	10	Various	N/A
Generic 2.1 mm DC Plug	D-0-P3	1	Various	N/A

† Cut to length

‡ Supplied in 12" lengths

* Required modification as per linked drawing

Table 22: Rotary DAQ parts for manufacture

Title	Part/Drawing No.	Qty.	Raw Material
Coupler Body	64 / D-1-1	1	4-3/4" x 3/4" aluminum tube or eq. round
Outer Bushing Plate	65 / D-1-2	1	7-1/2" x 4-1/8" 10 ga. sheet steel
Coupler Nut	66 / D-1-3	1	6" x 1" AISI 1045 round
DAQ Support Plate	73 / D-2-1-1	2	7" x 15-1/4" 10 ga. sheet aluminum
Take-off Plate	74 / D-2-2	1	3" x 13" 10 ga. sheet aluminum
Battery Mount	84 / D-4-1	2	4" x 4" x 1/8" x 9-3/8" HSS
CPU Backer	89 / D-5-1	1	7" x 9-3/4" 8 ga. sheet aluminum
DAQ Holder Plate	91 / D-6-1	1	1-1/2" x 7" 18 ga. sheet aluminum
DAQ Holder Pad	92 / D-6-2	1	1" x 5" x 1/4" EPDM sheet

Table 23: Rotary DAQ connection detail

Label	Components	Connectors	Description	Length
D-0-C1	D-3-0 to D-5-P1	93 / D-0-P1 → 93 / D-0-P1	22 AWG double conductor	15" min
D-0-C2	D-0-E to D-5-P1	As supplied	USB	As supplied
D-0-C3	D-3-0 to D-0-E	93 / D-0-P1 → D-0-P3	26 AWG double conductor	16-1/4"
D-0-C4	D-3-0 to Ext	93 / D-0-P1 → Solder	26 AWG double conductor (min)	approx. 6'
D-0-C5	D-0-E to Ext	Terminal	20 AWG K-type TC, Omega HH-K-20	N/A
D-0-C6	D-0-E to Ext	Terminal	20 AWG K-type TC, Omega HH-K-20	N/A

References

- [1] W.F. Hosford and R.M. Caddell. *Metal Forming: Mechanics and Metallurgy*. Mechanical engineering: Materials. ISBN 9780135885260. (Cited on page 18.)
- [2] J.A. Schey. *Introduction to manufacturing processes*. McGraw-Hill international editions: Industrial engineering series. ISBN 9780070552791. (Cited on page 21.)
- [3] E.J. Hearn. *Mechanics of Materials Volume 1: An Introduction to the Mechanics of Elastic and Plastic Deformation of Solids and Structural Materials*. ISBN 9780080523996. (Cited on page 21.)

Drawings

The following are the most recent design drawings/circuit diagrams for the stage. Note that some mechanical details may have been omitted/changed during the course of commissioning. The dimensions on the mechanical drawings may not reflect the current physical assembly; they have been included for reference only.

Rotary Tooling Assembly A: T-0A

BOM

ITEM NO.	PART NUMBER	DESCRIPTION	QTY.
1	T-1-0	MANDREL ASSM.	1
2	BL-1	330N BLANK (EXISTING)	1
3	T-2-3-0	CLAMP BLOCK 3 ASSM.	3
4	T-0-P4	1.5" x 1/4" QRP	3
5	T-2-1	CLAMP BLOCK 1	3
6	T-2-2-0	CLAMP BLOCK 2 ASSM.	3
7	T-0-P5	M16 SHCS 50 mm	3

NOTE 1: CONNECTION POINT TO ROTARY TOOLING ASSM. B: SEE DRAWING T-0B
 NOTE 2: 1/4" PIN PASSES THROUGH ITEM 8 AND ENGAGES ON THE OD OF ITEM 1 (3 PLCS)
 NOTE 3: ITEM 7 PASSES THROUGH ITEMS 6, 5 & 1 AND THREADS INTO ITEM 3 (3 PLCS)

RELEASE

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:	NAME	DATE
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MM	DRAWN	MJR 03/05/10
TOLERANCES:	CHECKED	
ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2°	ENG APPR.	
ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.2	MFG APPR.	
TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.05	Q.A.	
ALL DIAMETERS $\frac{Z}{0.2}$ $\frac{\varnothing}{0.2}$	COMMENTS:	
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5		
MATERIAL SEE DRAWINGS		
FINISH Ra 1.6 µm		
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		

REFERENCE		
TITLE:		
ROTARY TOOLING ASSM. A		
SIZE	DWG. NO.	REV
A	T-0A	0
SCALE: 1:10		WEIGHT:
		SHEET 1 OF 1

5 † 4 3 2 1

Mandrel Assembly: T-1-0

BOM

ITEM NO.	PART NUMBER	DESCRIPTION	QTY.
1	T-1-1-0	MANDREL WELDMENT	1
2	T-1-3	CENTERING PLATE	1
3	T-1-P2	M8 SHCS 20 mm	6
4	T-1-2	DRIVE CAP	1
5	T-1-P1	M16 SHCS 55 mm	6

NOTE 1: ITEM 3 PASSES THROUGH 2 AND THREADS INTO ITEM 1 (6 PLCS)
 NOTE 2: ITEM 5 PASSES THROUGH 1 AND THREADS INTO ITEM 4 (6 PLCS)

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:	NAME	DATE
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MM	DRAWN MJR	03/02/10
TOLERANCES:	CHECKED	
ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2°	ENG APPR.	
ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.2	MFG APPR.	
TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.05	Q.A.	
ALL DIAMETERS $\frac{Z}{\text{O}}$ 0.2	COMMENTS:	
	RO - ADDED 1.5° DRAFT	
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5		
MATERIAL SEE DRAWINGS		
FINISH Ra 1.6 µm		
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		

REFERENCE		
TITLE: MANDREL ASSM.		
SIZE A	DWG. NO. T-1-0	REV 1
SCALE: 1:10		WEIGHT:
		SHEET 1 OF 1

RELEASE

5 4 3 2 1

ITEM NO.	PART NUMBER	DESCRIPTION	QTY.
1	T-1-1-2	MANDREL INSERT	1
2	T-1-1-1	MANDREL	1

III

- SET MANDREL INSERT (T-1-1-2) AGAINST DATUM I
- WELD AS PER SECTION B-B
- FINISH MANDREL INSERT TO SIZE + DRILL & TAP

RELEASE

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:		NAME	DATE
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MM		DRAWN	MJR 03/02/10
TOLERANCES:		CHECKED	
ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2°		ENG APPR.	
ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.2		MFG APPR.	
TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.05		O.A.	
ALL DIAMETERS: $\frac{Z}{0.2}$ $\frac{O}{0.2}$		COMMENTS: R0 - ADDED 1.5° DRAFT	
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5			
MATERIAL AISI/SAE 4130			
FINISH Ra 1.6 µm			
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING			

MANUFACTURE		
TITLE: MANDREL WELDMENT		
SIZE A	DWG. NO. T-1-1-0	REV 1
SCALE: 1:5	WEIGHT:	SHEET 1 OF 2

5

↑

4

3

2

1

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:	NAME	DATE
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MM	DRAWN	MJR 03/02/10
TOLERANCES:	CHECKED	
ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2°	ENG APPR.	
ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.2	MFG APPR.	
TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.05	O.A.	
ALL DIAMETERS $\frac{Z}{\phi} 0.2$	COMMENTS:	
	R0 - ADDED 1.5° DRAFT	
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5		
MATERIAL		
AISI/SAE 4130		
FINISH		
Ra 1.6 µm		
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		

MANUFACTURE		
TITLE:		
MANDREL WELDMENT		
SIZE	DWG. NO.	REV
A	T-1-1-0	1
SCALE: 1:5	WEIGHT:	SHEET 2 OF 2

RELEASE

5

†

4

3

2

1

11

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:		NAME	DATE
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MM		DRAWN	MJR 03/02/10
TOLERANCES:		CHECKED	
ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2°		ENG APPR.	
ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.2		MFG APPR.	
TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.05		O.A.	
ALL DIAMETERS: $\frac{Z}{\text{O}}$ 0.2		COMMENTS:	
		R0 - ADDED 1.5° DRAFT	
		R1 - Ø302.1 CHANGED TO 302	
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5			
MATERIAL		FINISH	
AISI/SAE 4130		RZ 35	
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING			

MANUFACTURE		
TITLE:		
MANDREL		
SIZE	DWG. NO.	REV
A	T-1-1-1	2
SCALE: 1:5		WEIGHT:
		SHEET 2 OF 3

RELEASE

5 4 3 2 1

DETAIL H
SCALE 2 : 5

DETAIL I
SCALE 2 : 5

DETAIL J
SCALE 4 : 5
NOTE: DETAIL J IS TYPICAL FOR ALL 10 T/C BORES

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:		NAME	DATE
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MM		DRAWN	MJR 03/02/10
TOLERANCES:		CHECKED	
ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2°		ENG APPR.	
ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.2		MFG APPR.	
TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.05		O.A.	
ALL DIAMETERS: $\frac{Z}{\text{O}}$ 0.2		COMMENTS:	
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5		R0 - ADDED 1.5° DRAFT	
MATERIAL AISI/SAE 4130		R1 - Ø302.1 CHANGED TO 302	
FINISH RZ 35			
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING			

MANUFACTURE		
TITLE: MANDREL		
SIZE A	DWG. NO. T-1-1-1	REV 2
SCALE: 1:5	WEIGHT:	SHEET 3 OF 3

RELEASE

5 4 3 2 1

ii

viii

RELEASE

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:		NAME	DATE	MANUFACTURE	
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MM		DRAWN	MJR		
TOLERANCES:		CHECKED		TITLE: MANDREL INSERT	
ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2°		ENG APPR.			
ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.2		MFG APPR.			
TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.05		Q.A.			
ALL DIAMETERS $\frac{\square}{\circ}$ 0.2		COMMENTS:		SIZE	DWG. NO.
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5				A	T-1-1-2
MATERIAL					REV
AISI/SAE 4130					0
FINISH				SCALE: 1:5 WEIGHT:	
Ra 1.6 µm				SHEET 1 OF 1	
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING					

5 † 4 3 2 1

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:		NAME	DATE
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MM		DRAWN	MJR 01/21/10
TOLERANCES:		CHECKED	
ANGULAR: MACH ± 1° BEND ± 2°		ENG APPR.	
ONE PLACE DECIMAL ± 0.2		MFG APPR.	
TWO PLACE DECIMAL ± 0.05		Q.A.	
ALL DIAMETERS ∇ 0.2		COMMENTS:	
\varnothing 0.2		R0: Ø 295.7 CHANGED TO 295.9	
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5			
MATERIAL			
AISI 1020/1018			
FINISH			
Ra 1.6 µm			
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING			

MANUFACTURE		
TITLE:		
DRIVE CAP		
SIZE	DWG. NO.	REV
A	T-1-3	1
SCALE: 1:5	WEIGHT:	SHEET 1 OF 1

xi

x

RELEASE

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:	NAME	DATE
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MM	DRAWN MJR	01/21/10
TOLERANCES:	CHECKED	
ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2°	ENG APPR.	
ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.2	MFG APPR.	
TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.05	Q.A.	
ALL DIAMETERS \varnothing 0.2	COMMENTS:	
\varnothing 0.2		
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5		
MATERIAL AISI 1020/1018		
FINISH Ra 1.6 µm		
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		

MANUFACTURE		
TITLE: CENTERING PLATE		
SIZE A	DWG. NO. T-1-4	REV 0
SCALE: 1:5	WEIGHT:	SHEET 1 OF 1

5 † 4 3 2 1

Clamp Block 1: T-2-1

BOM

RELEASE

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED: DIMENSIONS ARE IN MM TOLERANCES: ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2° ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.2 TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.05 ALL DIAMETERS $\frac{H}{C} \begin{matrix} 0.2 \\ 0.2 \end{matrix}$		NAME	DATE	MANUFACTURE	
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5		DRAWN	MJR	22/01/10	TITLE:
MATERIAL AISI/SAE 4130		CHECKED			CLAMP BLOCK 1
FINISH Ra 1.6 µm		ENG APPR.			
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		MFG APPR.			
		Q.A.			
		COMMENTS: BREAK ALL SHARP EDGES		SIZE	DWG. NO.
				A	T-2-1
				REV.	0
				WEIGHT:	SHEET 1 OF 1

Clamp Block 2 Assembly: T-2-2-0

BOM

ITEM NO.	PART NUMBER	DESCRIPTION	QTY.
1	T-2-2-1	CLAMP BLOCK 2	1
2	T-2-2-P1	M8 x 22 SHCS - 91290A428	2
3	T-2-2-2	CLAMP PLATE	1

ix

R0	INITIAL RELEASE
R1	REDESIGN TO ALLOW FOR CLAMP PLATE

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:	NAME	DATE
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MM	DRAWN	MJR 11/24/10
TOLERANCES:	CHECKED	
ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2°	ENG APPR.	
ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.2	MFG APPR.	
TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.05	Q.A.	
ALL DIAMETERS	COMMENTS:	
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5		
MATERIAL		
VARIOUS		
FINISH		
Ra 1.6 µm		
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		

REFERENCE		
TITLE:		
CLAMP BLOCK 2 ASSEMBLY		
SIZE	DWG. NO.	REV
A	T-2-2-0	1
SCALE: 1:2	WEIGHT:	SHEET 1 OF 1

5 † 4 3 2 1

Clamp Block 2: T-2-2-1

BOM

AIX

R4.20
TYP

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:		NAME	DATE	MANUFACTURE TITLE: CLAMP PLATE		
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MM		DRAWN	MJR			11/24/10
TOLERANCES:		CHECKED				
ANGULAR: MACH $\pm 1^\circ$ BEND $\pm 2^\circ$		ENG APPR.				
ONE PLACE DECIMAL ± 0.2		MFG APPR.				
TWO PLACE DECIMAL ± 0.05		Q.A.				
ALL DIAMETERS $\begin{matrix} \text{Z} & 0.2 \\ \text{C} & 0.2 \end{matrix}$		COMMENTS:		SIZE	DWG. NO.	REV
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5				A	T-2-2-2	0
MATERIAL				SCALE: 1:1	WEIGHT:	SHEET 1 OF 1
3/8" COLD ROLLED PLATE						
FINISH						
Ra 0.4 μm						
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING						

5 † 4 3 2 1

RELEASE

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED: DIMENSIONS ARE IN MM TOLERANCES: ANGULAR: MACH±1° BEND ±2° ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.2 TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.05 ALL DIAMETERS $\begin{matrix} \text{H} \\ \text{O} \end{matrix} 0.2$	DRAWN	NAME	DATE
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5	MJR	MJR	22/01/10
MATERIAL AISI 1020/1018	CHECKED		
FINISH Ra 1.6 µm	ENG APPR.		
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING	MFG APPR.		
	Q.A.		
	COMMENTS:	BREAK ALL SHARP EDGES	

MANUFACTURE			
TITLE: CLAMP BLOCK 3			
SIZE	DWG. NO.	REV.	
A	T-2-3-1	0	
WEIGHT:		SHEET 1 OF 1	

1 AX

NOTE: 3.2 μm = 125 μin

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:		NAME	DATE	MANUFACTURE	
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MM [IN]		DRAWN	MJR		
TOLERANCES:		CHECKED		TITLE: CLAMP BLOCK 3 REWORK	
ANGULAR: MACH $\pm 1^\circ$ BEND $\pm 2^\circ$		ENG APPR.			
ONE PLACE DECIMAL ± 0.2		MFG APPR.		SIZE	
TWO PLACE DECIMAL ± 0.05		Q.A.		DWG. NO.	
ALL DIAMETERS $\frac{Z}{\text{M}}$ 0.02		COMMENTS:		REV	
M 0.02				A	
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5				T-2-3-RW	
MATERIAL				0	
4130, HRC 16				SCALE: 1:1	
FINISH				WEIGHT:	
Ra 1.6 μm				SHEET 1 OF 1	
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING					

5 4 3 2 1

Mandrel Loader: MH-0

ITEM NO.	PART NUMBER	DESCRIPTION	QTY.
1	LR-2-1	STEADY REST (EXISTING)	1
2	LR-2-1-1-0	STEADY REST SPIGOT (EXISTING)	1
3	T-0 (A/B)	MANDREL ASSM.	1
4	MH-0-P1	M16 EYEBOLT- 3040T17	2
5	MH-0-P2	7/32" TRADE x 2' CHAIN - 3410T74	1
6	MH-0-P3	1/2"-13 NUT 95505A605	1
7	MH-0-P4	1/2"-13 EYEBOLT 3013T491	1
8	MH-0-P5	1/2" POLY-P TIE DOWN 29925T24	1
9	MH-0-P6	7/16" x 8-1/8" TURN B. - 30315T33	2
10	M-1-0	LEVELING JIG	1

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED: DIMENSIONS ARE IN MM TOLERANCES: ANGULAR: MACH±1° BEND±2° ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.2 TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.05 ALL DIAMETERS INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5 MATERIAL: VARIOUS FINISH: N/A DO NOT SCALE DRAWING	NAME	DATE	REFERENCE TITLE: MANDREL LOADER
	DRAWN	MJR 06/28/10	
	CHECKED		
	ENG APPR.		
	MFG APPR.		
COMMENTS:			SIZE: A DWG. NO.: MH-0 REV: 0 SCALE: 1:2 WEIGHT: SHEET 1 OF 1

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5 4 3 2 1

Rotary Tooling Assembly: T-0B

BOM

ITEM NO.	PART NUMBER	DESCRIPTION	QTY.
1	T-3-0	DRIVESHAFT WELDMENT	1
2	T-0-P1	M12 SHCS 20 mm	6
3	LR-1	SPINDLE NOSE (EXISTING)	1
4	T-0-P2	M20 SHCS 55 mm	6
5	T-0-P3	M20 LOCKNUT	6

NOTE 1: ITEM 2 PASSES THROUGH ITEM 1 TO CONNECT TO ROTARY TOOLING ASSM. A: SEE DRAWING T-0A (6 PLCS)
 NOTE 2: ITEM 4 PASSES THROUGH ITEMS 1 & 3 AND THREADS INTO ITEM 5 (6 PLCS)

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:	NAME	DATE
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MM	DRAWN	MJR 03/05/10
TOLERANCES:	CHECKED	
ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2°	ENG APPR.	
ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.2	MFG APPR.	
TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.05	Q.A.	
ALL DIAMETERS $\frac{Z}{0.2}$ $\frac{O}{0.2}$	COMMENTS:	
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5		
MATERIAL SEE DRAWINGS		
FINISH Ra 1.6 µm		
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		

REFERENCE		
TITLE: ROTARY TOOLING ASSM. B		
SIZE A	DWG. NO. T-0B	REV 0
SCALE: 1:10 WEIGHT:		SHEET 1 OF 1

RELEASE

5 † 4 3 2 1

Drive Shaft: T-3-1

BOM

XX

RELEASE

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:	
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MM	
TOLERANCES:	
ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2°	
ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.2	
TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.05	
ALL DIAMETERS $\frac{\square}{\bigcirc}$ 0.2	
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5	
MATERIAL AISI 1020/1018	
FINISH Ra 1.6 µm	
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING	

	NAME	DATE
DRAWN	MJR	01/21/10
CHECKED		
ENG APPR.		
MFG APPR.		
Q.A.		

COMMENTS:

MANUFACTURE		
TITLE: DRIVE SHAFT		
SIZE A	DWG. NO. T-3-1	REV 0
SCALE: 1:5	WEIGHT:	SHEET 1 OF 1

5

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2

1

Ø 12.8 THRU
60° C-SINK 1.2
ON Ø 132.7
TYP

SECTION A-A
SCALE 1 : 1.5

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:		NAME	DATE	MANUFACTURE	
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MM TOLERANCES: ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2° ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.2 TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.05		DRAWN	MJR		
ALL DIAMETERS $\frac{Z}{\text{O}}$ 0.2		CHECKED		TITLE: NON-DRIVE SIDE FLANGE	
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5		ENG APPR.		SIZE A DWG. NO. T-3-2 REV 0	
MATERIAL AISI 1020/1018		MFG APPR.		SCALE: 1:5 WEIGHT: SHEET 1 OF 1	
FINISH Ra 1.6 µm		Q.A.			
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		COMMENTS:			

RELEASE

5 4 3 2 1

ixx

RELEASE

Rotary Tooling Assembly: R-0

BOM

ITEM NO.	PART NUMBER	DESCRIPTION	QTY.
1	LR-2	TOOL HOLDER BLOCK	1
2	R-1-0	ROLLER ARM ASSM.	1
3	R-2	REAR BRACE	1
4	R-3	FRONT BRACE	1

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RELEASE

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:	NAME	DATE
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MM	DRAWN	MJR 02/22/10
TOLERANCES:	CHECKED	
ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2°	ENG APPR.	
ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.2	MFG APPR.	
TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.05	Q.A.	
ALL DIAMETERS $\frac{Z}{0.2}$	COMMENTS:	
$\frac{C}{0.2}$		
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5		
MATERIAL		
SEE DRAWINGS		
FINISH		
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		

REFERENCE		
TITLE:		
ROLLER TOOLING ASSM		
SIZE	DWG. NO.	REV
A	R-0	0
SCALE: 1:1	WEIGHT:	SHEET 1 OF 1

5

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2

1

ITEM NO.	PART NUMBER	DESCRIPTION	QTY.
1	R-1-2	ROLLER SUPPORT ARM	1
2	R-1-4	ROLLER SHAFT	1
3	R-1-1-0	ROLLER ASSM	1
4	R-1-3	OUTBOARD SPACER	1
5	R-1-P1	SKF MB5 LOCK WASHER	1
6	R-1-P2	SKF KM5 LOCKNUT	1
7	R-1-P3	M16 BOLT	1

XXIV

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:	NAME	DATE
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MM	DRAWN	MJR 02/23/10
TOLERANCES:	CHECKED	
ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2°	ENG APPR.	
ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.2	MFG APPR.	
TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.05	Q.A.	
ALL DIAMETERS $\frac{Z}{0.2}$	COMMENTS:	
$\frac{C}{0.2}$		
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5		
MATERIAL SEE DRAWINGS		
FINISH N/A		
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		

REFERENCE		
TITLE:		
ROLLER SUPPORT ASSM		
SIZE	DWG. NO.	REV
A	R-1-0	0
SCALE: 1:1	WEIGHT:	SHEET 1 OF 2

RELEASE

5 † 4 3 2 1

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED: DIMENSIONS ARE IN MM TOLERANCES: ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2° ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.2 TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.05 ALL DIAMETERS $\begin{matrix} \text{H} & \text{h} \\ \text{7} & \text{7} \\ \text{0.2} & \text{0.2} \end{matrix}$ $\begin{matrix} \text{M} & \text{m} \\ \text{0.2} & \text{0.2} \end{matrix}$	DRAWN	NAME	DATE	REFERENCE TITLE: <h2 style="text-align: center;">ROLLER SUPPORT ASSM.</h2>	
	CHECKED	MJR	02/23/10		
	ENG APPR.				
	MFG APPR.				
	Q.A.				
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5 MATERIAL SEE DRAWINGS FINISH Ra 1.6 μm DO NOT SCALE DRAWING	COMMENTS: BREAK ALL SHARP EDGES			SIZE DWG. NO. A R-1-0 REV. 0 WEIGHT: SHEET 2 OF 2	

Roller Assembly: R-1-1-0

BOM

ITEM NO.	PART NUMBER	DESCRIPTION	QTY.
1	R-1-1-1	ROLLER BODY	1
2	R-1-1-P1	SKF 32005 X/Q BEARING	2
3	R-1-1-P2	SKF CR 38x48x4 HM4 R SEAL	2

XXVI

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:	NAME	DATE
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MM	DRAWN	MJR 02/23/10
TOLERANCES:	CHECKED	
ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2°	ENG APPR.	
ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.2	MFG APPR.	
TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.05	Q.A.	
ALL DIAMETERS $\frac{Z}{0.2}$	COMMENTS:	
$\frac{C}{0.2}$		
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5		
MATERIAL SEE DRAWINGS		
FINISH N/A		
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		

REFERENCE		
TITLE: ROLLER ASSM		
SIZE	DWG. NO.	REV
A	R-1-1-0	0
SCALE: 1:1	WEIGHT:	SHEET 1 OF 1

RELEASE

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RELEASE

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:		NAME	DATE
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MM		DRAWN	MJR 03/08/10
TOLERANCES:		CHECKED	
ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2°		ENG APPR.	
ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.2		MFG APPR.	
TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.05		Q.A.	
ALL DIAMETERS $\frac{Z}{\text{O}}$ 0.2		COMMENTS: R0: $\phi 48$ CHANGED TO 47.98, $\phi 47$ CHANGED TO 46.99	
O 0.2			
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5		SIZE	
MATERIAL 8620 IMPACTO		DWG. NO.	
FINISH Ra 1.6 μm		R-1-1-1	
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		REV	
		1	

MANUFACTURE		
TITLE: ROLLER BODY		
SCALE: 1:5	WEIGHT:	SHEET 1 OF 1

5 † 4 3 2 1

Tapered roller bearings, single row, metric bearings

Principal dimensions			Basic load ratings		Fatigue load limit P_u	Speed ratings		Mass kg	Designation
d	D	T	dynamic	static		Reference speed	Limiting speed		
mm			kN		kN	r/min			-
25	47	15	27	32,5	3,25	11000	14000	0,11	32005 X/Q

Calculation factors
 e 0,43
 Y 1,4
 Y₀ 0,8

Radial shaft seals with low cross sectional height

Dimensions			Designation
Shaft d ₁	Bore d ₂	Nominal seal width b	
mm			-
38	48	4	G 38x48x4

Roller Support Arm: R-1-2

BOM

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UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:		NAME	DATE	MANUFACTURE TITLE: OUTBOARD SPACER			
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MM		DRAWN	MJR			03/08/10	
TOLERANCES:		CHECKED					
ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2°		ENG APPR.					
ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.2		MFG APPR.					
TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.05		Q.A.					
ALL DIAMETERS $\begin{matrix} \text{H} \\ \text{H} \end{matrix} 0.2$		COMMENTS: R0: ID DIMENSION CHANGED			SIZE	DWG. NO.	REV
$\text{M} 0.2$					A	R-1-3	1
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5					SCALE: 1:1	WEIGHT:	SHEET 1 OF 1
MATERIAL							
AISI 1020							
FINISH							
Ra 1.6 μm							
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING							

RELEASE

5 † 4 3 2 1

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RELEASE

5 4 3 2 1

MB(L) locking washers

Dimensions			Mass	Designations	
d	d ₂	B		Locking washer	Appropriate lock nut
mm			kg	-	
25	42	1,25	0,006	MB 5	KM 5

XXXX

KM(L) lock nuts with locking washer

Thread size	Dimensions			Axial load carrying capacity static	Mass	Designations Lock nut	Appropriate locking washer	spanner
	d_3	B	G					
mm	mm			kN	kg	-		
25	38	7	M 25x1.5	31,5	0,028	KM 5	MB 5	HN 5-6

Rear Brace: R-2

BOM

DETAIL B
SCALE 1.5 : 1

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:		NAME	DATE	MANUFACTURE	
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MM		DRAWN	MJR	03/08/10	TITLE: REAR BRACE
TOLERANCES:		CHECKED			
ANGULAR: MACH±1° BEND±2°		ENG APPR.			
ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.2		MFG APPR.			
TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.05		Q.A.			SIZE
ALL DIAMETERS: \varnothing 0.2 \varnothing 0.2 \varnothing 0.2 \varnothing 0.2		COMMENTS: R0: CHANGED CHANNEL DETAIL		DWG. NO.	REV
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5				A	R-2
MATERIAL CRS 1020/1035				1	
FINISH Ra 6.3 µm				SCALE: 1:2	WEIGHT:
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING				SHEET 1 OF 1	

RELEASE

5 † 4 3 2 1

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RELEASE

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:		NAME	DATE	MANUFACTURE		
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MM		DRAWN	MJR			03/08/10
TOLERANCES:		CHECKED		TITLE:		
ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2°		ENG APPR.		FRONT BRACE		
ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.2		MFG APPR.				
TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.05		Q.A.		SIZE	DWG. NO.	REV
ALL DIAMETERS $\begin{matrix} \text{M} \\ \text{L} \end{matrix} \begin{matrix} 0.2 \\ 0.2 \end{matrix} \begin{matrix} \text{P} \\ \text{L} \end{matrix} \begin{matrix} 0.2 \\ 0.2 \end{matrix}$		COMMENTS:		A	R-3	1
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5		R0: CHANGED NOTCH DETAIL		SCALE: 1:2	WEIGHT:	SHEET 1 OF 1
MATERIAL						
CRS 1020/1035						
FINISH						
Ra 6.3 µm						
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING						

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3

2

1

XXXXVII

RELEASE

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:		NAME	DATE	REFERENCE		
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MM		DRAWN	MJR			03/23/10
TOLERANCES:		CHECKED		TITLE: HEATING SYSTEM		
ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2°		ENG APPR.				
ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.2		MFG APPR.				
TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.05		Q.A.				
ALL DIAMETERS $\frac{Z}{0.2}$		COMMENTS:		SIZE	DWG. NO.	REV
$\frac{\text{C}}{0.2}$				A	H-0	0
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5				SCALE: 1:50		WEIGHT:
MATERIAL						SHEET 1 OF 2
SEE DRAWINGS						
FINISH						
N/A						
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING						

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4

3

2

1

ITEM NO.	PART NUMBER	DESCRIPTION	QTY.
1	H-1-0	TORCH HOLDER	1
2	H-2-0	DISTRIBUTOR	1
3	H-3-0	HOSE SUPPORT	1
4	H-0-P1	60" SAE 1/2" F-FLARE END HOSE	1
5	H-0-P1	60" SAE 1/2" F-FLARE END HOSE	1
6	H-0-P1	60" SAE 1/2" F-FLARE END HOSE	1
7	H-0-P1	60" SAE 1/2" F-FLARE END HOSE	1
8	H-0-P2	72" 1/4xPOL WHIP	1
9	H-0-P3	20/40 LB PROPANE TANK	1
10	BL-1	FORMING BLANK	1

XXXXVIII

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:	NAME	DATE
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MM	DRAWN	MJR 03/29/10
TOLERANCES:	CHECKED	
ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2°	ENG APPR.	
ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.2	MFG APPR.	
TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.05	Q.A.	
ALL DIAMETERS $\frac{Z}{0.2}$	COMMENTS:	
$\frac{C}{0.2}$		
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5		
MATERIAL SEE DRAWINGS		
FINISH N/A		
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		

REFERENCE		
TITLE: HEATING SYSTEM		
SIZE	DWG. NO.	REV
A	H-0	0
SCALE: 1:50		WEIGHT:
		SHEET 2 OF 2

5 † 4 3 2 1

Torch Holder: H-1-0

BOM

ITEM NO.	PART NUMBER	DESCRIPTION	QTY.
1	H-1-2	SUPPORT ARM	1
2	H-1-P1	3-1/4" ID X 3/8"-16 U BOLT	2
3	H-1-3	MOUNT PLATE	1
4	H-1-1-0	TORCH ASSM.	4
5	H-1-P2	3/8" NUT	6
6	H-1-P3	3/8x1" BOLT	2
7	H-1-P4	3/8" WASHER	2
8	H-1-P5	1/4" WASHER	8
9	H-1-P6	1/4"x1-1/8" BOLT	5
10	H-1-P7	1/4" NUT	5
11	H-1-4	BINDING PLATE	1

XXXX

RELEASE

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:	NAME	DATE
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MM	DRAWN	MJR 03/29/10
TOLERANCES:	CHECKED	
ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2°	ENG APPR.	
ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.2	MFG APPR.	
TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.05	Q.A.	
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5	COMMENTS:	
MATERIAL		
SEE DRAWINGS		
FINISH		
N/A		
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		

REFERENCE		
TITLE:		
TORCH HOLDER		
SIZE	DWG. NO.	REV
A	H-1-0	0
SCALE: 1:2	WEIGHT:	SHEET 1 OF 1

5 4 3 2 1

Torch: H-1-1-0

BOM

ITEM NO.	PART NUMBER	DESCRIPTION	QTY.
1	H-1-1-P1	1/4" NPT x 5" NIPPLE	1
2	H-1-1-P2	MALE M20 TO 1/4" F-NPT ADAPTER	1
3	H-1-1-P3	3119 EXACT TIP	1
4	H-0-P1	60" SAE 1/2" F-FLARE END HOSE	1
5	H-1-1-P4	1/4" NPT HEX COUPLER	1
6	H-1-1-P5	1/4" NPT TO LH ADAPTER	1

1x

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:	NAME	DATE
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MM	DRAWN MJR	03/29/10
TOLERANCES:	CHECKED	
ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2°	ENG APPR.	
ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.2	MFG APPR.	
TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.05	Q.A.	
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5	COMMENTS:	
MATERIAL SEE DRAWINGS	0: CHANGED FROM SAE FITTING TO 45° LH FITTING	
FINISH N/A		
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		

REFERENCE		
TITLE:		
TORCH ASSM		
SIZE	DWG. NO.	REV
A	H-1-1-0	1
SCALE: 1:2	WEIGHT:	SHEET 1 OF 1

RELEASE

5 † 4 3 2 1

Brass Pipe Fittings and Pipe

Part Number: 9176K162	\$12.32 Each
Shape	Nipple
Nipple Type	Threaded Ends
Pipe to Pipe Connection	NPT x NPT
Schedule	40
System of Measurement	Inch
Pipe/Thread Size	1/4"
Length	5"
Inside Diameter	.364"
Outside Diameter	.54"
Wall Thickness	.088"
Material	Chrome-Plated Cast Red Brass
Specifications Met	American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM)
ASTM Specification	ASTM B43, ASTM B456-03, ASTM B687-99

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UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:	NAME	DATE
DIMENSIONS ARE IN INCHES	DRAWN MJR	04/01/10
TOLERANCES:	CHECKED	
ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2°	ENG APPR.	
ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.1	MFG APPR.	
TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.01	Q.A.	
THREE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.005	COMMENTS:	
FRACTIONAL: ±1/32		
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5		
MATERIAL 2X3X1/4 MSA		
FINISH N/A		
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		

MANUFACTURE		
TITLE:		
SUPPORT ARM		
SIZE	DWG. NO.	REV
A	H-1-2	0
SCALE: 1:5	WEIGHT:	SHEET 1 OF 1

RELEASE

5 4 3 2 1

Mount Plate: H-1-3

BOM

xlili

RELEASE

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:	NAME	DATE
DIMENSIONS ARE IN INCHES	DRAWN	MJR 04/02/10
TOLERANCES:	CHECKED	
ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2°	ENG APPR.	
ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.1	MFG APPR.	
TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.01	Q.A.	
THREE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.005	COMMENTS:	
FRACTIONAL: ±1/32		
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5		
MATERIAL		
2X2X3/16 MSA		
FINISH		
N/A		
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		

MANUFACTURE		
TITLE:		
MOUNT PLATE		
SIZE	DWG. NO.	REV
A	H-1-3	0
SCALE: 1:5	WEIGHT:	SHEET 1 OF 1

5 † 4 3 2 1

A11X

RELEASE

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:		NAME	DATE	MANUFACTURE		
DIMENSIONS ARE IN INCHES TOLERANCES: ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2° ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.1 TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.01 THREE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.005 FRACTIONAL: ±1/32		DRAWN	MJR			04/02/10
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5		CHECKED		TITLE:		
MATERIAL 2x1/8 MSFB		ENG APPR.		BINDING PLATE		
FINISH N/A		MFG APPR.				
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		Q.A.		SIZE	DWG. NO.	REV
		COMMENTS:		A	H-1-4	0
				SCALE: 1:2	WEIGHT:	SHEET 1 OF 1

5 † 4 3 2 1

U-Bolts

Part Number: 3042T19	\$2.41 Each
Material Type	Steel
Finish	Plain
Type	Clamping
Thread Size	3/8"-16
For Outside Diameter (A)	3-1/4"
Length (B)	4-13/16"
Thread Length (C)	1-1/2"
Work Load Limit	Not Rated
Furnished With	Two locking nuts.
WARNING	Not rated for work load limit.

ITEM NO.	PART NUMBER	DESCRIPTION	QTY.
1	H-2-1	DISTRIBUTOR BODY	1
2	H-2-P1	1/4" NPT HEX BARB	5
3	H-2-P2	1" TO 1/4" NPT HEX BUSHING	1
4	H-2-2	DISTRIBUTOR MOUNT PLATE	2
5	H-2-P3	3-1/4" ID X 3/8"-16 U BOLT	2
6	H-2-P4	3/8" NUT	8
7	H-2-P5	2" X 3/8"-16 SQUARE BOLT	2
8	H-2-P6	SV-S121 SOLENOID VALVE	1
9	H-0-P1	60" SAE 1/2" F-FLARE END HOSE	4
10	H-2-P7	67CH-743 0-30 PSI REGULATOR	1
11	H-2-P9	GEN. SERVICE PRESSURE GAUGE	1
12	H-2-P10	1-1/2" X 1/4" NPT NIPPLE	3
13	H-2-3	REGULATOR SUPPORT	1
14	H-2-P11	1/4" NPT PANEL MOUNT FITTING	1
15	H-2-P12	SHORT HANDLE 1/4" NPT F-F VALVE	4
16	H-2-P13	1/4" M-NPT TO LH ADAPTER	4
17	H-2-P8	1/4" NPT TEE	1

RELEASE

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:

DIMENSIONS ARE IN MM
 TOLERANCES:
 ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2°
 ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.2
 TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.05

INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5

MATERIAL SEE DRAWINGS

FINISH

DO NOT SCALE DRAWING

	NAME	DATE
DRAWN	MJR	03/29/10
CHECKED		
ENG APPR.		
MFG APPR.		
Q.A.		

COMMENTS:
 0: CHANGED TO ACCOMMODATE LH TORCH HOSE

REFERENCE		
TITLE: DISTRIBUTOR		
SIZE A	DWG. NO. H-2-0	REV 1
SCALE: 1:2	WEIGHT:	SHEET 1 OF 1

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:	NAME	DATE
DIMENSIONS ARE IN INCHES	DRAWN	MJR 04/01/10
TOLERANCES:	CHECKED	
ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2°	ENG APPR.	
ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.1	MFG APPR.	
TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.01	Q.A.	
THREE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.005	COMMENTS:	
FRACTIONAL: ±1/32		
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5		
MATERIAL		
2"x2" CRS BAR STOCK		
FINISH		
N/A		
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		

MANUFACTURE		
TITLE:		
DISTRIBUTOR BODY		
SIZE	DWG. NO.	REV
A	H-2-1	0
SCALE: 1:5	WEIGHT:	SHEET 1 OF 1

RELEASE

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5 † 4 † 3 † 2 † 1

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RELEASE

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:		NAME	DATE	MANUFACTURE TITLE: REGULATOR SUPPORT		
DIMENSIONS ARE IN INCHES		DRAWN	MJR			04/26/10
TOLERANCES:		CHECKED				
ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2°		ENG APPR.				
ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.1		MFG APPR.				
TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.01		Q.A.				
THREE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.005		COMMENTS:			SIZE A DWG. NO. H-2-3 REV 1	
FRACTIONAL: ±1/32		0: ADDED CUTOUT TO ELIMINATE REGULATOR BODY INTERFERENCE, ADDED HIDDEN LINES TO SHOW HOLE OFFSET				
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5						
MATERIAL					SCALE: 1:5	
2x1/8 MSFB & 2X2X1/8 MSA					WEIGHT:	
FINISH					SHEET 1 OF 1	
N/A						
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING						

5

4

3

2

1

Brass Pipe Fittings and Pipe

Part Number: 9171K214	\$4.95 Each
Shape	Nipple
Nipple Type	Hex Nipple
Pipe to Pipe Connection	NPT x NPT
System of Measurement	Inch
Pipe/Thread Size	1/4"
Length	1-29/64"
Material	Precision-Machined Yellow Brass
Maximum Pressure @ 72° F	4100 psi
Maximum Pressure Note	For steam, maximum pressure is 1560 psi @ 300° F.
Specifications Met	American National Standards Institute (ANSI), American Society of Mechanical Engineers (ASME)
ANSI Specification	ANSI B1.20.1
ASME Specification	ASME B1.20.1

Brass Pipe Fittings and Pipe

Part Number: 4429K461	\$6.20 Each
Shape	Bushing
Bushing Type	Hex Bushing (Male x Female)
Pipe to Pipe Connection	NPT x NPT
System of Measurement	Inch
Pipe/Thread Size	1" reduced to 1/4"
Material	Cast Red Brass
Maximum Pressure @ 72° F	200 psi
Maximum Pressure Note	For steam, maximum pressure is 125 psi @ 400° F.
Specifications Met	American National Standards Institute (ANSI), American Society of Mechanical Engineers (ASME), American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM)
ANSI Specification	ANSI B1.20.1, ANSI B16.15
ASTM Specification	ASTM B584
ASME Specification	ASME B1.20.1

U-Bolts

Part Number: 3060T44	\$2.46 Each
Material Type	Steel
Finish	Zinc-Plated
Type	Square
Thread Size	$\frac{3}{8}$ "-16
For Width (A)	2"
Length (B)	2-5/8"
Thread Length (C)	1-1/2"
Work Load Limit	1,090 lbs.
Furnished With	Two hex nuts and two flat washers.
WARNING	Never exceed work load limits.

Brass Pipe Fittings and Pipe

Part Number: 4429K251	\$6.05 Each
Shape	Tee
Tee Type Pipe to Pipe	Female Tee
Pipe to Pipe Connection	NPT x NPT
System of Measurement	Inch
Pipe/Thread Size	1/4"
Material	Cast Red Brass
Maximum Pressure @ 72° F	200 psi
Maximum Pressure Note	For steam, maximum pressure is 125 psi @ 400° F.
Specifications Met	American National Standards Institute (ANSI), American Society of Mechanical Engineers (ASME), American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM)
ANSI Specification	ANSI B1.20.1, ANSI B16.15
ASTM Specification	ASTM B584
ASME Specification	ASME B1.20.1

Pressure Gauges

Part Number:	32255K71	\$18.07 Each
Gauge Type	Pressure	
Service Type	General Service	
For Use With	Acetylene, Carbon Dioxide, Compressed Air, Oxygen, Welding	
Accuracy	±2% Mid-Scale (Grade B)	
NIST Certification	Without Certificate of Calibration	
Dial Type	Dry	
Connection Size and Type	1/4" NPT Male	
Connection Location	Bottom	
Connection Material	Brass	
Sensor Type	Bourdon Pressure Tube	
Sensor Material (Internals)	Brass	
Case Material	Polycarbonate	
Lens Material	Polycarbonate	
Units of Measure	psi	
Operating Pressure Range (psi)	0 to 30	
Numerical Increments (psi)	5	
Graduation Marks (psi)	1	
Round Dial Diameter	2"	
Process Temperature Range	-40° to +140° F	
Ambient Temperature Range	-40° to +140° F	
Specifications Met	American Society of Mechanical Engineers (ASME), Underwriters Laboratories (UL)	
ASME Specifications Met	B40.1, Level IV (Oxygen)	
UL Specifications Met	252A	

Brass Pipe Fittings and Pipe

Part Number: 9149K22	\$3.43 Each
Shape	Nipple
Nipple Type	Threaded Ends
Pipe to Pipe Connection	NPT x NPT
Schedule	80
System of Measurement	Inch
Pipe/Thread Size	1/4"
Length	1-1/2"
Inside Diameter	.302"
Outside Diameter	.54"
Wall Thickness	.119"
Material	Cast Red Brass
Specifications Met	American National Standards Institute (ANSI), American Society of Mechanical Engineers (ASME), American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM)
ANSI Specification	ANSI B1.20.1
ASTM Specification	ASTM B43, ASTM B687-99
ASME Specification	ASME B1.20.1

Brass Pipe Fittings and Pipe

Part Number: **5483T93**

\$8.65 per Pack of 2

Shape	Coupling
Coupling Type	Panel Mount Coupling
Pipe to Pipe Connection	NPT x NPT
System of Measurement	Inch
Pipe/Thread Size	1/4"
Panel Hole Size	25/32"
Material	Nickel-Plated Yellow Brass
Maximum Pressure @ 72° F	1000 psi
Specifications Met	Not Rated
Notes	Also called a bulkhead fitting. Includes a nut and a lockwasher.

Hose Support: H-3-0

BOM

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RELEASE

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Hose Bracket: H-3-1

BOM

Clamps

Metal Clamps

Choose from a variety of metal clamps with either one or two mounting holes to secure pipe, conduit, and tubing. Fasteners not included.

- Heavy duty** clamps are extra thick so they're less likely to bend under heavy loads.
- Steel** clamps are good where corrosion is not a factor.
- Zinc-plated steel** clamps offer good corrosion resistance in most environments.
- Type 304 stainless steel** clamps provide excellent corrosion resistance.
- Type 316 stainless steel** clamps offer maximum corrosion resistance.
- Brass** clamps have excellent conductivity and good corrosion resistance.

One-Hole Mount for Pipe and Rigid Conduit

For OD	For Pipe/ Rigid Conduit Size	Lg. x Wd.	Thick.	Mtg. Hole Dia.	Pkg. Qty.	Per Pkg.
Steel						
1/8"	1/8"	1 3/16" x 3/8"	3/64"	3/16"	50	9434T16 \$4.13
1/8"	1/4"	1 3/16" x 3/8"	3/64"	3/16"	50	9434T17 4.42
1 1/16"	3/8"	1 3/8" x 3/4"	3/64"	1/4"	50	9434T18 5.90
1 3/16"	1/2"	1 7/8" x 7/8"	3/64"	1/4"	50	9434T19 5.98
1 1/2"	3/4"	2 1/8" x 7/8"	3/64"	1/4"	50	9434T22 8.04
1 3/16"	1"	2 3/4" x 1"	1/8"	1/4"	50	9434T24 11.78
Zinc-Plated Steel						
1 1/16"	1 1/16"	3 1/4" x 7/8"	3/32"	1/4"	10	9435T66 4.63
2 3/8"	2"	4 1/16" x 7/8"	1/8"	1/4"	10	9435T68 11.66
Heavy Duty Zinc-Plated Steel						
1 3/16"	1/2"	2" x 7/8"	1/8"	1/4"	25	9434T71 10.04
1 1/16"	3/4"	2 3/8" x 7/8"	1/8"	1/4"	25	9434T72 10.71
1 3/16"	1"	2 1/8" x 7/8"	1/8"	1/4"	25	9434T73 14.27
1 1/16"	1 1/4"	3 1/8" x 1"	1/8"	5/16"	10	9434T74 8.75
1 7/8"	1 1/2"	3 3/4" x 1 1/4"	1/8"	3/8"	5	9434T75 6.03
2 3/8"	2"	4 3/8" x 1 1/4"	3/8"	3/8"	5	9434T76 9.03
Type 304 Stainless Steel						
1 3/16"	1/2"	1 7/8" x 7/8"	3/64"	1/4"	5	8897T11 3.41
1 1/16"	3/4"	2 3/8" x 7/8"	3/64"	1/4"	5	8897T12 4.63
1 3/16"	1"	2 1/8" x 7/8"	3/64"	1/4"	5	8897T13 5.91
1 1/16"	1 1/4"	3 1/8" x 1"	3/32"	5/16"	1	8897T14 1.80
1 7/8"	1 1/2"	3 1/8" x 1"	1/8"	3/8"	1	8897T15 2.93
2 3/8"	2"	4 3/8" x 1 1/4"	3/8"	3/8"	1	8897T16 3.96
Type 316 Stainless Steel						
1 3/16"	1/2"	1 3/4" x 5/8"	1/16"	5/64"	1	9750T71 1.51
Brass						
1 3/16"	1/2"	1 7/8" x 7/8"	3/64"	1/4"	10	9488T11 9.66
1 3/16"	1"	2 1/8" x 1"	1/8"	1/4"	1	9488T12 1.90

One-Hole Mount for Thinwall (EMT) Conduit

For OD	For Thinwall (EMT) Conduit Size	Lg. x Wd.	Thick.	Mtg. Hole Dia.	Pkg. Qty.	Per Pkg.
Steel						
1 1/16"	1/2"	1 5/8" x 3/4"	3/64"	1/4"	50	9434T18 \$5.90
1 5/16"	3/4"	1 7/8" x 7/8"	3/64"	1/4"	50	9434T28 7.40
1 3/16"	1"	2 3/8" x 7/8"	3/64"	1/4"	50	9434T23 9.90
1 1/2"	1 1/4"	2 1/8" x 1"	1/8"	1/4"	25	9434T25 8.19
Heavy Duty Zinc-Plated Steel						
1 1/16"	1/2"	1 3/8" x 7/8"	1/8"	1/4"	25	9434T77 9.09
1 3/16"	3/4"	2 1/8" x 7/8"	1/8"	1/4"	25	9434T78 10.73
1 3/16"	1"	2 1/8" x 7/8"	1/8"	1/4"	10	9434T79 5.96
Type 304 Stainless Steel						
1 1/16"	1/2"	1 1/8" x 7/8"	3/64"	1/4"	5	8897T21 3.33
1 5/16"	3/4"	1 7/8" x 7/8"	3/64"	1/4"	5	8897T22 3.86
1 3/16"	1"	2 1/8" x 7/8"	3/64"	1/4"	5	8897T23 5.54

One-Hole Mount for Tubing

For OD	For Tube Size	Lg. x Wd.	Thick.	Mtg. Hole Dia.	Pkg. Qty.	Per Pkg.
Steel						
1/8"	1/8"	1 3/16" x 1/2"	1/32"	3/16"	50	9434T11 \$3.06
3/16"	3/16"	7/8" x 1/2"	1/32"	3/16"	50	9434T12 3.19
1/4"	1/4"	1 1/8" x 1/2"	1/32"	3/16"	50	9434T13 3.14
5/16"	5/16"	1 5/16" x 1/2"	1/32"	3/16"	50	9434T14 3.58
3/8"	3/8"	1 3/8" x 5/8"	3/64"	3/16"	50	9434T15 4.00
1/2"	1/2"	1 5/8" x 5/8"	3/64"	3/16"	50	9434T17 4.42
3/4"	3/4"	1 7/8" x 3/4"	3/64"	1/4"	50	9434T27 6.22
1"	1"	2 1/8" x 7/8"	3/64"	1/4"	50	9434T28 8.04
1 1/2"	1 1/2"	2 3/16" x 1"	1/8"	1/4"	25	9434T25 8.19
Brass						
1/8"	1/8"	1 3/16" x 1/2"	1/32"	3/16"	25	9488T15 6.87
3/16"	3/16"	7/8" x 1/2"	1/32"	3/16"	25	9488T16 7.13
1/4"	1/4"	1" x 1/2"	1/32"	3/16"	25	9488T17 7.13
5/16"	5/16"	1 5/16" x 1/2"	1/32"	3/16"	25	9488T18 7.56
3/8"	3/8"	1 3/8" x 5/8"	3/64"	3/16"	25	9488T19 7.78
1/2"	1/2"	1 5/8" x 5/8"	3/64"	3/16"	25	9488T21 9.90
3/4"	3/4"	1 7/8" x 3/4"	3/64"	1/4"	10	9488T22 6.72
1 1/2"	1 1/2"	3" x 1"	1/8"	1/4"	1	9488T24 2.24

Two-Hole Mount for Pipe and Rigid Conduit

For OD	For Pipe/ Rigid Conduit Size	Lg. x Wd.	Thick.	Mtg. Hole Dia. (A)	Pkg. Qty.	Per Pkg.
Steel						
3/16"	1/4"	1 3/8" x 5/8"	1/32"	1/8"	1 1/16"	50 9439T41 \$4.74
1 3/16"	3/8"	2 1/2" x 3/4"	1/32"	3/16"	1 1/16"	50 9439T42 5.67
1 3/16"	1/2"	2 7/8" x 3/4"	1/32"	3/16"	1 1/16"	50 9439T43 6.63
1 1/8"	3/4"	2 1/8" x 3/4"	1/32"	3/16"	2 1/8"	50 9439T44 6.96
1 5/8"	1"	3 1/8" x 3/4"	1/32"	3/16"	2 1/8"	50 9439T24 8.64
1 11/16"	1 1/4"	4 3/8" x 7/8"	3/64"	1/4"	3 1/4"	25 9439T23 6.93
Heavy Duty Steel						
1 3/16"	1/2"	4 3/8" x 1 1/4"	1/8"	7/16"	2 7/8"	1 3039T14 1.44
1 1/8"	3/4"	4 5/8" x 1 1/4"	1/8"	7/16"	3"	1 3039T15 1.47
1 5/16"	1"	4 3/4" x 1 1/4"	1/8"	7/16"	3 3/8"	1 3039T16 1.52
1 11/16"	1 1/4"	5 1/8" x 1 1/4"	1/8"	7/16"	3 3/4"	1 3039T17 1.68
1 7/8"	1 1/2"	5 5/8" x 1 1/4"	1/8"	7/16"	4 1/4"	1 3039T18 2.06
2 3/8"	2"	5 13/16" x 1 1/4"	1/8"	7/16"	4 1/2"	1 3039T19 2.22
2 7/8"	2 1/2"	6 5/8" x 1 1/4"	1/4"	7/16"	5 1/4"	1 3039T21 3.72
3 1/2"	3"	7 5/8" x 1 1/4"	1/4"	7/16"	6"	1 3039T22 3.92
4 1/2"	4"	8 13/16" x 1 1/2"	1/4"	1/2"	7 7/8"	1 3039T24 4.67
Zinc-Plated Steel						
1 3/16"	1"	3 1/8" x 3/4"	3/32"	1 3/16"	2 3/8"	10 9439T11 6.05
1 7/8"	1 1/2"	4 3/8" x 1"	3/32"	3/16"	3 7/8"	10 9439T12 7.39
2 3/8"	2"	5 1/8" x 1 1/4"	3/32"	1 1/2"	3 7/8"	10 9439T13 9.59
2 7/8"	2 1/2"	6 5/8" x 1 1/4"	3/32"	1 3/8"	4 1/8"	1 9439T14 1.29
3 1/2"	3"	7 1/8" x 1 1/4"	1/8"	1 3/8"	5 1/2"	1 9439T16 2.22
4"	3 3/4"	8 3/4" x 1 1/4"	3/16"	2 1/2"	6 1/8"	1 9439T17 3.86
4 1/2"	4"	9 1/8" x 1 1/4"	3/16"	2 1/2"	6 1/8"	1 9439T18 4.17
Heavy Duty Zinc-Plated Steel						
1 3/16"	1/2"	4 3/8" x 1 1/4"	1/8"	7/16"	2 7/8"	1 9439T31 2.10
1 1/8"	3/4"	4 5/8" x 1 1/4"	1/8"	7/16"	3"	1 9439T32 2.10
1 5/16"	1"	4 3/4" x 1 1/4"	1/8"	7/16"	3 3/8"	1 9439T33 2.22
1 11/16"	1 1/4"	5 1/8" x 1 1/4"	1/8"	7/16"	3 3/4"	1 9439T34 2.53
1 7/8"	1 1/2"	5 5/8" x 1 1/4"	1/8"	7/16"	4 1/4"	1 9439T35 3.04
2 3/8"	2"	5 13/16" x 1 1/4"	1/8"	7/16"	4 1/2"	1 9439T36 3.35
2 7/8"	2 1/2"	6 5/8" x 1 1/4"	1/4"	7/16"	5 1/4"	1 9439T37 5.19
3 1/2"	3"	7 5/8" x 1 1/4"	1/4"	7/16"	6"	1 9439T38 5.66
4 1/2"	4"	8 13/16" x 1 1/2"	1/4"	1/2"	7 7/8"	1 9439T39 7.21

Two-Hole Mount for Thinwall (EMT) Conduit

For OD	For Thinwall (EMT) Conduit Size	Lg. x Wd.	Thick.	Mtg. Hole Dia. (A)	Pkg. Qty.	Per Pkg.
Steel						
1 1/16"	1/2"	2 9/16" x 3/4"	1/32"	3/16"	1 13/16"	50 9429T34 \$4.48
1 5/16"	3/4"	2 3/8" x 3/4"	1/32"	3/16"	2 1/8"	50 9429T35 4.96
1 3/16"	1"	3 3/8" x 3/4"	1/32"	3/16"	2 5/8"	50 9429T36 6.24
1 1/2"	1 1/4"	3 7/8" x 7/8"	3/64"	1/4"	2 5/8"	50 9429T37 9.58
1 3/4"	1 1/2"	4 5/8" x 1"	3/64"	1/4"	3 1/8"	25 9429T38 7.93
2 3/16"	2"	5" x 1"	3/64"	1/4"	3 3/4"	25 9429T39 9.92
Type 304 Stainless Steel						
3/16"	3/8"	1 1/8" x 5/8"	1/32"	3/16"	1 1/4"	1 8874T41 1.04
1 1/16"	1/2"	2 1/8" x 5/8"	1/32"	3/16"	1 1/8"	1 8874T42 1.21
1 5/16"	3/4"	2 3/4" x 3/4"	1/32"	1 7/16"	1 7/8"	1 8874T43 1.36
1 3/16"	1"	3 3/8" x 3/4"	3/64"	1 7/16"	2 1/8"	1 8874T44 1.62
1 1/2"	1 1/4"	3 1/2" x 7/8"	3/64"	1 7/16"	2 3/8"	1 8874T45 3.01
1 3/4"	1 1/2"	3 7/8" x 1 1/4"	1/8"	1 7/16"	3 1/4"	1 8874T46 3.29
2 3/16"	2"	4 5/8" x 1 1/4"	1/8"	7/16"	3 1/8"	1 8874T47 5.92

MIN. CLEARANCE THROUGH
MANDREL BODY

3.50
Ø88.90

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UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:		NAME	DATE	MANUFACTURE		
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MM		DRAWN	MJR			06/16/10
TOLERANCES:		CHECKED		TITLE:		
ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2°		ENG APPR.		MANDREL TC INSTALLATION		
ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.2		MFG APPR.				
TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.05		Q.A.		SIZE	DWG. NO.	REV
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5		COMMENTS:		A	T-4-0	0
MATERIAL				SCALE: 1:10		WEIGHT:
FINISH						SHEET 2 OF 2
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING						

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ixi

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TC Harness: T-4-2-0

BOM

ITEM NO.	PART NUMBER	DESCRIPTION	QTY.
1	T-4-2-1	LEFT TC HARNESS BRACKET	1
2	T-4-2-2	RIGHT TC HARNESS BRACKET	1
3	T-4-2-P1	1/4-20x5/8" HEX STANDOFF	2
4	T-4-2-P2	1/4x1" CS	2
5	T-4-2-P3	1/4-20x6-25/32" THREADED ROD	1
6	T-4-2-P4	TC BUNDLE (10 PCS)	1
7	T-4-2-P5	#4-40x6-25/32" THREADED ROD	1
8	T-4-2-P6	1/4-20x7/32" NUT	2
9	T-4-2-P7	#4-40x3/32" NUT	2

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:
 DIMENSIONS ARE IN MM
 TOLERANCES:
 ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2°
 ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.2
 TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.05

INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5

MATERIAL
 VARIOUS

FINISH
 Ra 1.6 µm

DO NOT SCALE DRAWING

	NAME	DATE
DRAWN	MJR	06/15/10
CHECKED		
ENG APPR.		
MFG APPR.		
Q.A.		

COMMENTS:

MANUFACTURE		
TITLE: TC HARNESS		
SIZE A	DWG. NO. T-4-2-0	REV 0
SCALE: 1:10 WEIGHT:		SHEET 1 OF 2

5 † 4 3 2 1

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UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED: DIMENSIONS ARE IN MM TOLERANCES: ANGULAR: MACH $\pm 1^\circ$ BEND $\pm 2^\circ$ ONE PLACE DECIMAL ± 0.2 TWO PLACE DECIMAL ± 0.05	NAME	DATE	MANUFACTURE TITLE: LEFT TC HARNESS BRACKET	
	DRAWN	MJR		06/16/10
	CHECKED			
	ENG APPR.			
	MFG APPR.			
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5 MATERIAL 12 GAUGE IMS SHEET FINISH Ra 1.6 μ m DO NOT SCALE DRAWING	Q.A.		COMMENTS: BREAK ALL SHARP EDGES	
	SIZE	DWG. NO.	REV.	
	A	T-4-2-1	0	
	WEIGHT:	SHEET 1 OF 1		

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED: DIMENSIONS ARE IN MM TOLERANCES: ANGULAR: MACH±1° BEND ±2° ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.2 TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.05	DRAWN	NAME	DATE	MANUFACTURE TITLE: RIGHT TC HARNES BRACKET
	CHECKED	MJR	06/16/10	
	ENG APPR.			
	MFG APPR.			
	Q.A.			
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5	COMMENTS: BREAK ALL SHARP EDGES			SIZE DWG. NO. T-4-2-2 REV. 0
MATERIAL 12 GAUGE MS SHEET FINISH Ra 1.6 µm DO NOT SCALE DRAWING	WEIGHT:			SHEET 1 OF 1

DAQ Assembly: D-0

↪ BOM

ITEM NO.	PART NUMBER	DESCRIPTION	QTY.
1	D-2-0	DAQ SUPPORT ASSM	1
2	D-0-P1	DAQ SHAFT	1
3	D-1-0	COUPLER ASSM	1
4	D-5-0	CPU ASSM	1
5	D-0-E	USB-2416	1
6	D-0-P2-0	GAS SPRING ASSM	4
7	D-4-0	BATTERY ASSM	1
8	D-6-0	DAQ RETAINER	1
9	D-3-0	POWER MANAGER	1
10	D-0-P1	SWITCHCRAFT 760 DC PLUG	4
11	D-0-P2	0.75" CABLE TIE	10
12	D-0-P3	CUI PP3-002A DC PLUG	1
13	D-0-C1	2 x 22 AWG MIN. CNDTR.	1
14	D-0-C2	USB-A TO USB-B SHEILDED	1
15	D-0-C3	2 x 26 AWG MIN. CNDTR.	1
16	D-0-C4	2 X 26 AWG MIN. CNDTR.	1
17	D-0-C5	20 AWG K-TYPE TC CABLE x 5	1
18	D-0-C6	20 AWG K-TYPE TC CABLE x 5	1

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UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:		NAME	DATE
DIMENSIONS ARE IN INCHES		DRAWN	MJR 03/29/09
TOLERANCES:		CHECKED	
ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2°		ENG APPR.	
ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.1		MFG APPR.	
TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.01		Q.A.	
THREE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.005		COMMENTS:	
FRACTIONAL: ±1/32			
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5			
MATERIAL VARIOUS			
FINISH N/A			
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING			

REFERENCE		
TITLE: DAQ ASSEMBLY		
SIZE A	DWG. NO. D-0	REV 1
SCALE: 1:1	WEIGHT:	SHEET 1 OF 3

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UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED: DIMENSIONS ARE IN INCHES TOLERANCES: ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2° ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.1 TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.01 THREE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.005 FRACTIONAL: ±1/32 INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5 MATERIAL VARIOUS FINISH N/A DO NOT SCALE DRAWING	NAME	DATE	REFERENCE TITLE: <h2 style="text-align: center;">DAQ ASSEMBLY</h2>		
	DRAWN	MJR			03/29/11
	CHECKED				
	ENG APPR.				
	MFG APPR.				
	COMMENTS:		SIZE	DWG. NO.	REV
			A	D-0	1
			SCALE: 1:1	WEIGHT:	SHEET 3 OF 3

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NOTE: BASED ON MCMASTER CARR P/N 1497K956, AS REC'D LENGTH: 18"

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED: DIMENSIONS ARE IN INCHES TOLERANCES: ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2° ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.1 TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.01 THREE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.005 FRACTIONAL: ±1/32 INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5 MATERIAL 3/4"x18" 95 HRB KEYED SHAFT FINISH N/A DO NOT SCALE DRAWING	DRAWN	MJR	10/01/10	MODIFICATION TITLE: DAQ SHAFT		
	CHECKED					
	ENG APPR.			SIZE	DWG. NO.	REV
	MFG APPR.			A	D-0-P1	0
	Q.A.			SCALE: 1:2	WEIGHT:	SHEET 1 OF 1
COMMENTS:						

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Gas Spring Assembly: D-0-P2-0

↶ BOM

ITEM NO.	PART NUMBER	DESCRIPTION	QTY.
1	D-0-P2-P1	MC 9416K14-15 LB	1
2	D-0-P2-P2	MC 9416K86	2

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UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:		NAME	DATE	REFERENCE	
DIMENSIONS ARE IN INCHES TOLERANCES: ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2° ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.1 TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.01 THREE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.005 FRACTIONAL: ±1/32		DRAWN	MJR		
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5		CHECKED			TITLE: GAS SPRING ASSM
MATERIAL		ENG APPR.			
N/A		MFG APPR.			
FINISH		Q.A.			
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		COMMENTS:		SIZE	DWG. NO.
				A	D-0-P2-0
					REV
					0
				SCALE: 1:2	WEIGHT:
					SHEET 1 OF 1

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Ball Socket Fitting: D-0-P2-P2

↶ BOM

lxxii

		PART NUMBER	9416K86
		Glass-Filled Nylon Ball Socket Fitting	
© 2009 McMaster-Carr Supply Company <small>Unless otherwise specified, dimensions are in inches. Information in this drawing is provided for reference only.</small>			

Coupler Assembly: D-1-0

BOM

ITEM NO.	PART NUMBER	DESCRIPTION	QTY.
1	D-1-1	COUPLER BODY	1
2	D-1-P1	3/4" SHAFT COLLAR 6435K16	1
3	D-1-P2	SLEEVE BUSHING 6126K49	1
4	D-1-2	OUTER BUSHING PLATE	1
5	D-1-P3	GAS SPRING JOINT 9512K73	4
6	D-1-3	COUPLER NUT	1
7	D-1-P4	5/16"-18 NUT 93827A219	4
8	D-1-P5	1/4"-20 x 9/16" CS 92620A539	4
9	D-1-P6	FLANGE BUSHING 6389K437	1

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UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:
 DIMENSIONS ARE IN INCHES
 TOLERANCES:
 ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2°
 ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.1
 TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.01
 THREE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.005
 FRACTIONAL: ±1/32

INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5
 MATERIAL N/A
 FINISH N/A
 DO NOT SCALE DRAWING

	NAME	DATE
DRAWN	MJR	10/01/10
CHECKED		
ENG APPR.		
MFG APPR.		
Q.A.		

COMMENTS:

REFERENCE		
TITLE: COUPLER ASSM		
SIZE A	DWG. NO. D-1-0	REV 0
SCALE: 1:2	WEIGHT:	SHEET 1 OF 1

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LXXXIV

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2

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Ixxxvi

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:

DIMENSIONS ARE IN INCHES
 TOLERANCES:
 ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2°
 ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.1
 TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.01
 THREE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.005
 FRACTIONAL: ±1/32

INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5

MATERIAL
AISI 1045
 FINISH N/A

DO NOT SCALE DRAWING

	NAME	DATE
DRAWN	MJR	10/01/10
CHECKED		
ENG APPR.		
MFG APPR.		
Q.A.		

COMMENTS:

MANUFACTURE		
TITLE:		
COUPLER NUT		
SIZE A	DWG. NO. D-1-3	REV 0
SCALE: 1:5	WEIGHT:	SHEET 1 OF 1

5 † 4 3 2 1

Shaft Collar: D-1-P1

BOM

lxxvii

McMASTER-CARR	PART NUMBER 6435K16
http://www.mcmaster.com © 2007 McMaster-Carr Supply Company	Black-Oxide Steel One-Piece Clamp-On Shaft Collar
Unless otherwise specified, dimensions are in inches. Information in this drawing is provided for reference only.	

Sleeve Bearings

Part Number: **6126K49**

\$1.87 Each

Material	Plastic
Plastic Type	Nylon 642
Type	Thrust Bearings
Thrust Bearing Type	Snap In
For Shaft Diameter (Inside Diameter)	3/4"
Inside Diameter Tolerance	+ .001"
Outside Diameter	1"
Small End Outside Diameter	27/32"
Flange Thickness	1/32" (both ends)
Fits Sheet Hole Diameter	13/16"
Sheet Material Thickness	.072" to .135"
Load (P Max)	Not Rated
Speed (V Max)	Not Rated
Load at Speed (PV Max)	Not Rated
Temperature Range	-40° to +280° F
Specifications Met	Not Rated

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McMASTER-CARR CAD

PART
NUMBER

9512K73

<http://www.mcmaster.com>
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Information in this drawing is provided for reference only.

Zinc-Plated Steel
Ball Stud

Sleeve Bearings

Part Number:	6389K437	\$8.43 per Pack of 1
Material	Plastic	
Plastic Type	Nylon	
Type	Flanged Sleeve Bearings	
For Shaft Diameter (Inside Diameter)	3/4"	
Inside Diameter Tolerance	+ .002" to + .008"	
Outside Diameter	1"	
Outside Diameter Tolerance	+ .001" to + .007"	
Flange Outside Diameter	1-1/4"	
Flange Thickness	5/32"	
Length	1"	
Length Tolerance	± .015"	
Load (P Max)	400	
Speed (V Max)	360	
Load at Speed (PV Max)	3,000	
Temperature Range	-20° to +250° F	
Specifications Met	Not Rated	

DAQ Support Assembly: D-2-0

BOM

ITEM NO.	PART NUMBER	DESCRIPTION	QTY.
1	D-2-2	TAKE-OFF PLATE	1
2	D-2-P1	FLANGED SHAFT COLLAR 9684T3	1
3	D-2-P2	3/16" X 3/16" KEYSTOCK 99020A420	1
4	D-2-P3	5/16"-18 NUT 93827A219	4
5	D-2-P4	GAS SPRING JOINT 9512K73	4
6	D-2-P5	1/4"-20 X 9/16" CS 92620A539	3
7	D-2-P6	1/4"-20 LOCKNUT 97135A210	5
8	D-2-1-0	DAQ SUPPORT PLATE ASSM	2
9	D-2-P7	1/4-20 x 2-1/2" CS 91236A552	1

LXXXI

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:

DIMENSIONS ARE IN INCHES
 TOLERANCES:
 ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2°
 ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.1
 TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.01
 THREE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.005
 FRACTIONAL: ±1/32

INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5

MATERIAL VARIOUS

FINISH N/A

DO NOT SCALE DRAWING

	NAME	DATE
DRAWN	MJR	03/29/11
CHECKED		
ENG APPR.		
MFG APPR.		
Q.A.		

COMMENTS: ADDED MOUNTING HARDWARE FOR POWER MANAGEMENT

REFERENCE

TITLE:

DAQ SUPPORT ASSM.

SIZE	DWG. NO.	REV
A	D-2-0	1

SCALE: 1:10 WEIGHT: SHEET 1 OF 1

5 4 3 2 1

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UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:		NAME	DATE	MANUFACTURE	
DIMENSIONS ARE IN INCHES		DRAWN	MJR		
TOLERANCES:		CHECKED			TITLE:
ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2°		ENG APPR.			DAQ SUPPORT PLATE
ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.1		MFG APPR.			
TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.01		O.A.			SIZE
THREE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.005		COMMENTS:			DWG. NO.
FRACTIONAL: ±1/32					REV
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5					A
MATERIAL					D-2-1-1
10 GA. MIN. ALUMINUM SHEET					0
FINISH					SCALE: 1:5
AS REC'D					WEIGHT:
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING					SHEET 1 OF 1

5 4 3 2 1

Take Off Plate: D-2-2

BOM

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Flanged Shaft Collar: D-2-P1

BOM

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McMASTER-CARR CAD

PART NUMBER

9684T3

<http://www.mcmaster.com>
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 Information in this drawing is provided for reference only.

Black-Oxide Steel Flanged
 One-Piece Clamp-On Shaft Collar

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UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:	NAME	DATE
DIMENSIONS ARE IN INCHES	DRAWN	MJR 03/29/11
TOLERANCES:	CHECKED	
ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2°	ENG APPR.	
ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.1	MFG APPR.	
TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.01	Q.A.	
THREE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.005	COMMENTS:	
FRACTIONAL: ±1/32		
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5		
MATERIAL VARIOUS		
FINISH N/A		
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		

REFERENCE		
TITLE:		
POWER MANAGER		
SIZE	DWG. NO.	REV
A	D-3-0	0
SCALE: 1:5	WEIGHT:	SHEET 1 OF 2

5 † 4 3 2 1

DAQ Assembly: D-0

BOM

ITEM NO.	PART NUMBER	DESCRIPTION	QTY.
1	D-3-EM1	CTRL CCT	1
2	D-3-P1	1/4x0.1" WASHER 91090A105	2
3	D-3-P2	1/4" EPDM WASHER	2
4	D-3-P3	1/4-20 x 2-1/2" CS 91236A552	1
5	D-3-P4	1/4-20 x 7/16" CS 92620A539	1
6	D-3-P5	GEN. BIND POST (RD)	1
7	D-3-P6	SWITCHCRAFT 712A	3
8	D-3-P7	T 1-3/4 LED CLIP	4
9	D-3-P8	T 1-3/4 LED RETAIN.	4
10	D-3-P9	T 1-3/4 RED LED	1
11	D-3-P10	T 1-3/4 AMBER LED	1
12	D-3-P11	T 1-3/4 GREEN LED	2
13	D-3-P12	NKK M2023LLIW01 DPDT	1
14	D-3-P13	D-3-P12 CRUSH WASHER	1
15	D-3-P14	D-3-P12 NUT	2
16	D-3-P15	#6-32 x 1" NYLON STANDOFF	3
17	D-3-P16	D-3-P5/P23 NUT	2
18	D-3-P17	D-3-P6 WASHER	3
19	D-3-P18	D-3-P6 NUT	3
20	D-3-P19	HAMMOND 1411J BASE	1
21	D-3-P20	HAMMOND 1411J COVER	1
22	D-3-P21	#6 SELF TAP. MS	4
23	D-3-P22	#6-32 x 7/16" MS 90272A147	6
24	D-3-P23	GEN. BIND POST (BLK)	1

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UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED: DIMENSIONS ARE IN INCHES TOLERANCES: ANGULAR: MACH±1° BEND±2° ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.1 TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.01 THREE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.005 FRACTIONAL: ±1/32	DRAWN	MJR	03/29/11
	CHECKED		
	ENG APPR.		
	MFG APPR.		
	Q.A.		
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5	COMMENTS:		
MATERIAL VARIOUS			
FINISH N/A			
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING			

REFERENCE		
TITLE: POWER MANAGER		
SIZE A	DWG. NO. D-3-0	REV 0
SCALE: 1:5	WEIGHT:	SHEET 2 OF 2

5 † 4 † 3 † 2 † 1

Power Control Circuit: D-3-EL1

BOM

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2.5 mm DC Jack: D-3-P6

BOM

XC

MATERIAL:

- MOUNTING BUSHING: COPPER ALLOY, NICKEL PLATED.
- HOUSING: THERMOPLASTIC, BLACK
- PIN, SPRING AND TERMINALS: COPPER ALLOY, SILVER PLATED.
- INSULATORS: PHENOLIC
- HARDWARE: HEX NUT: COPPER ALLOY, NICKEL PLATED
FLAT WASHER: STEEL, NICKEL PLATED
(NOT SHOWN)

CIRCUIT DIAGRAM

CUSTOMER DRAWING

CAD/CAM DWG. NO.
712A-CD
SHEET 1 OF 1

G					ECO 42292	8-31-99	JL	DK	★ STAR SYMBOL DENOTES CRITICAL DIMENSION. SEE SPC ENGINEERING STANDARD ES-7001.	THIS DRAWING DESCRIBES A DESIGN CONSIDERED PROPRIETARY IN NATURE, DEVELOPED AND MANUFACTURED BY SWITCHCRAFT INC. AND IS RELEASED ON A CONFIDENTIAL BASIS FOR IDENTIFICATION PURPOSE ONLY.				
F					ECO 42055	9-8-95	DA	TAD	UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED	FINISH	WTOH	INCH	TEMPER	
E					ECO 42054	9-8-95	DA	TAD	1. ALL DIMENSIONS IN INCHES. TWO PLACE DECIMAL 0.01 THREE PLACE DECIMAL 0.005 ANGLES 90.0°	MATERIAL SPEC. NO.				
C					ECO 42044	9-8-95	DA	TAD	ALL DIA'S CONCENTRIC WITHIN .005 T.I.R.	FIRST USED ON		SCALE 1 = 0.125		
B					ECO 42051	9-8-95	DA	TAD	2. REMOVE ALL BURRS	DATE DRAWN 10-4-93		APP'D		
A					ECO 41942	3-10-95	KC	GRJ	3. MAKE NO DIMENSIONAL ALLOWANCES FOR APPLIED FINISHES, I.E., PLATING, PAINTING, ETC.	BY RS		TAD		
X					FIRST DRAWN	10-4-93	RS	GRJ	4. HOLES ON THE SAME CENTERLINE MUST BE ALIGNED WITHIN .005	10-11-93		10-11-93		
ISSUE					CHANGE NO.	DATE	BY	APP'D	NAME POWER JAX				PART NO. 712A	ISSUE 6
REVISIONS					DO NOT SCALE DRAWING									

Series M

Miniature Toggles

A General Specifications

toggle
rocker
pushbutton
illuminated
programmable
keylock
rotary
slide
tactile
litt
touch
indicator
accessories
supplement

Electrical Capacity (Resistive Load)

- Power Level (silver):** 6A @ 125V AC & 3A @ 250V AC
4A @ 30V DC for On-None-On & On-None-Off; 3A @ 30V DC for all other circuits
- Logic Level (gold):** 0.4VA maximum @ 28V AC/DC maximum (Applicable Range 0.1mA ~ 0.1A @ 20mV ~ 28V)
- Logic/Power Level (gold over silver):** Combines silver & gold ratings
Note: Find additional explanation of dual rating & operating range in Supplement section.

Other Ratings

- Contact Resistance:** 10 milliohms maximum for silver; 20 milliohms maximum for gold
- Insulation Resistance:** 1,000 megohms minimum @ 500V DC
- Dielectric Strength:** 1,000V AC minimum between contacts for 1 minute minimum;
1,500V AC minimum between contacts and case for 1 minute minimum
- Mechanical Life:** 100,000 operations minimum; 50,000 operations minimum for flat, locking & splashproof devices
- Electrical Life:** 25,000 operations minimum for silver; 50,000 operations minimum for gold;
50,000 operations minimum for silver at 3A @ 125V AC
- Angle of Throw:** 25°

Materials & Finishes

- Toggle:** Brass with chrome plating
- Bushing:** Brass with nickel plating
- Case:** Diallyl phthalate resin (UL94V-0)
- Movable Contactor:** Phosphor bronze with silver or gold plating
- Movable Contacts:** Silver alloy (code W); copper with gold plating (code G); or silver alloy with gold plating (code A)
- Stationary Contacts:** Silver with silver plating (code W); copper or brass with gold plating (code G);
or silver with gold plating (code A)
- Terminals:** Copper or brass with silver plating; or copper or brass with gold plating
- Frame:** Stainless steel
- Support Bracket:** Brass with tin plating

Environmental Data

- Operating Temp Range:** -30°C through +85°C (-22°F through +185°F)
- Humidity:** 90 ~ 95% humidity for 96 hours @ 40°C (104°F)
- Vibration:** 10 ~ 55Hz with peak-to-peak amplitude of 1.5mm traversing the frequency range & returning in 1 minute; 3 right angled directions for 2 hours
- Shock:** 50G (490m/s²) acceleration (tested in 6 right angled directions, with 5 shocks in each direction)
- Sealing:** Splashproof bushing options B3, D3, D8, L3, & L8, which have o-rings inside & outside the bushing, meet IP67 of IEC60529 Standards.

Installation

- Mounting Torque:** 3.0Nm (26.55 lb•in) double nut for large bushing;
1.5Nm (13 lb•in) double nut & 0.7Nm (6 lb•in) single nut for all other bushings

Processing

- Soldering:** Wave Soldering (PC version) for Gold: See Profile A in Supplement section.
Manual Soldering for Gold: See Profile A in Supplement section.
Wave Soldering (PC version) for Silver: See Profile B in Supplement section.
Manual Soldering for Silver: See Profile B in Supplement section.
Note: Lever must be in OFF (center) position while soldering.
- Cleaning:** These devices are not process sealed. Hand clean locally using alcohol based solution.

Standards & Certifications

- Flammability Standards:** UL94V-0 for case
- UL:** File No. E44145
All models recognized at 6A @ 125V AC, 3A @ 250V AC or 0.4VA maximum @ 28V DC maximum.
Add "/U" to end of part number to order UL mark on switch.
Add "/CUL" to end of part number to order cULus mark on switch.
- CSA:** File No. 023535_0_000
All models recognized at 6A @ 125V AC or 3A @ 250V AC or 0.4VA maximum @ 28V maximum.
Add "/C" to end of part number to order CSA mark on switch.

Miniature Toggles

Series M

Distinctive Characteristics

Antirootation design, standard on noncylindrical levers, mates toggle and bushing; bottom of toggle has two flattened sides which fit into a complementary opening inside bushing.

Antijamming design protects contacts from damage due to excessive downward force on actuator.

High torque bushing construction prevents rotation or separation from frame during installation.

High insulating barriers increase isolation of circuits in multipole devices and provide added protection to contact points.

Molded diallyl phthalate case has a UL flammability rating of 94V-0.

Epoxy sealed terminals prevent entry of solder flux and other contaminants.

Prominent external insulating barriers increase insulation resistance and dielectric strength.

Interlocked actuator block, lever, and interior guide prevent switch failure due to biased lever movement.

Clinching of frame to case well above base and terminals provides 1,500V dielectric strength.

-
Bushing Mount
Page A48
-
Bracket PC Mount
Page A60
-
Angle PC Mount
Page A66

A

Terminals

Enclosure

Pushbuttons

Illuminated PB

Programmable

Keypads

Printers

Slides

Toggles

Tilt

Touch

Indicators

Accessories

Supplement

D-Cell Assembly: D-4-P1-0

BOM

ITEM NO.	PART NUMBER	DESCRIPTION	QTY.
1	D-4-P1-P1	BH2DL BATTERY HOLDER	1
2	D-4-P1-P2	D-CELL BATTERY	2
3	D-4-P1-P3	#5 TOOTH LOCK WASHER 91114A006	2
4	D-4-P1-P4	#5-40 X 3/8" MS 90283A126	2
5	D-4-P1-P5	#5-40 LOCKNUT 90633A006	2

NOTE: ITEM 4 PASSES THRU ITEM 3,1 AND D-4-1/D-4-2, THREADING INTO ITEM 5.

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UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:
 DIMENSIONS ARE IN INCHES
 TOLERANCES:
 ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2°
 ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.1
 TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.01
 THREE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.005
 FRACTIONAL: ±1/32

INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5
 MATERIAL: VARIOUS
 FINISH: N/A
 DO NOT SCALE DRAWING

	NAME	DATE
DRAWN	MJR	10/11/10
CHECKED		
ENG APPR.		
MFG APPR.		
Q.A.		

COMMENTS:

REFERENCE		
TITLE: D-CELL ASSM		
SIZE A	DWG. NO. D-4-P1-0	REV 0
SCALE: 1:2	WEIGHT:	SHEET 1 OF 1

5 4 3 2 1

Battery Holder: D-4-P1-P1

↶ BOM

DATE	SYM	REVISION RECORD	AUTH	DR.	CK.
12/14/00	A	Changed Mounting Holes Dimensions.	T.B.	B.S.	
9/23/06	B	ADDED "ROHS COMPLIANT"	T.B.	B.S.	
1/12/08	C	RANGE WAS "RANGEE"	T.B.	B.S.	

ORDERING CODE BH2D

SOLDER LUGS	= L
(6") WIRE LEADS	= W
9VOLT TYPE SNAPS	= SF
BUMP PLATES	= B

XCviii

SPECIFICATIONS:

- Plastic material - polypropylene
- Flammability Rating-UL94 HB, UL File No. E216959
- Temperature Range: -10°C to +100°C
- Springs - nickel plated spring steel
- Wire - 152.4 mm Long 26 AWG, UL1007, CSA - TR-64, 300V, 80° C.
- Rivets - Brass, nickel plated
- 9 Volts Snaps - Brass, nickel plated
- Contact Resistance: Under 50mΩ for +/- contacts per EIA-540J000
- ROHS COMPLIANT

Note: Dimensions in mm. (inches)

TOLERANCES (EXCEPT AS NOTED)		Memory Protection Devices, Inc. 200 Broad Hollow Road, Farmingdale, New York 11735	
DECIMAL			
+ .5 (.020")			APPROVED BY
FRACTIONAL	TITLE		
+ .8 (.030")	TWO "D" CELL HOLDER		
ANGULAR	DATE	DRAWING NUMBER	
+ 3°	1/12/2008	BH2DL	

MOTOMA Ni-MH D9000

MOTOMA POWER
WWW.MOTOMA.CN

SPECIFICATIONS

Normal voltage		1.2V
Capacity(0.2C ₅)	Minimum	9000mAh
	Typical	9050mAh
Typical internal impedance		less than 15mΩ
Standard charge		900mA at 15hrs.
Standard discharge		1800mA to 1.0V

General Characteristics

Important notice: The above specifications are subject to change without prior notice.

ITEM NO.	PART NUMBER	DESCRIPTION	QTY.
1	D-5-1	CPU BACKER	1
2	D-5-P2	1/4"-20 X 3/4" FLAT SHCS 91253A540	4
3	D-5-P3	SLEEVE BUSHING 6126K49	1
4	D-5-P4	1/4" EPDM RUBBER WASHER 90130A029	10
5	D-5-P5	1/4"-20 X 1" FLANGE HEX CS 92316A542	6
6	D-5-P6	1/4"-20 LOCKNUT 97135A210	6
7	D-5-P7	HIGH DAMP GROMMET 9311K137	6
8	D-5-0-P1	SERENER G-05 ASSM	1

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:	NAME	DATE
DIMENSIONS ARE IN INCHES	DRAWN	MJR 11/10/10
TOLERANCES:	CHECKED	
ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2°	ENG APPR.	
ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.1	MFG APPR.	
TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.01	Q.A.	
THREE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.005	COMMENTS:	
FRACTIONAL: ±1/32		
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5		
MATERIAL		
VARIOUS		
FINISH		
N/A		
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		

REFERENCE		
TITLE:		
CPU ASSM		
SIZE	DWG. NO.	REV
A	D-5-0	0
SCALE: 1:5	WEIGHT:	SHEET 1 OF 1

5 † 4 3 2 1

ci

DAQ Retainer: D-6-0

↶ BOM

ITEM NO.	PART NUMBER	DESCRIPTION	QTY.
1	D-6-1	DAQ HOLDER PLATE	1
2	D-6-2	DAQ HOLDER PAD	1
3	D-6-P1	1/4"-20 LOCKNUT 97135A210	2

cii

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:		NAME	DATE	REFERENCE		
DIMENSIONS ARE IN INCHES TOLERANCES: ANGULAR: MACH $\pm 1^\circ$ BEND $\pm 2^\circ$ ONE PLACE DECIMAL ± 0.1 TWO PLACE DECIMAL ± 0.01 THREE PLACE DECIMAL ± 0.005 FRACTIONAL: $\pm 1/32$		DRAWN	MJR			03/29/11
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5		CHECKED			TITLE: DAQ RETAINER	
MATERIAL VARIOUS		ENG APPR.				
FINISH N/A		MFG APPR.				
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		Q.A.				
		COMMENTS:		SIZE	DWG. NO.	REV
				A	D-6-0	0
				SCALE: 1:2	WEIGHT:	SHEET 1 OF 1

5

↑

4

3

2

1

ciii

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:

DIMENSIONS ARE IN INCHES
 TOLERANCES:
 ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2°
 ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.1
 TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.01
 THREE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.005
 FRACTIONAL: ±1/32

INTERPRET GEOMETRIC
 TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5

MATERIAL
 18 GA. ALUMINUM SHEET

FINISH
 N/A

DO NOT SCALE DRAWING

	NAME	DATE
DRAWN	MJR	03/29/11
CHECKED		
ENG APPR.		
MFG APPR.		
Q.A.		

COMMENTS:

MANUFACTURE		
TITLE: DAQ HOLDER PLATE		
SIZE A	DWG. NO. D-6-1	REV 0
SCALE: 1:2	WEIGHT:	SHEET 1 OF 1

5

4

3

2

1

civ

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:		NAME	DATE	MANUFACTURE	
DIMENSIONS ARE IN INCHES		DRAWN	MJR		
TOLERANCES:		CHECKED			TITLE: DAQ HOLDER PAD
ANGULAR: MACH ±1° BEND ±2°		ENG APPR.			
ONE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.1		MFG APPR.			
TWO PLACE DECIMAL ±0.01		Q.A.			
THREE PLACE DECIMAL ±0.005		COMMENTS:			
FRACTIONAL: ±1/32					SIZE
INTERPRET GEOMETRIC TOLERANCING PER: ASME Y14.5					DWG. NO.
MATERIAL					REV
EPDM MATTING					A
FINISH					D-6-2
N/A					0
DO NOT SCALE DRAWING					SCALE: 1:2
					WEIGHT:
					SHEET 1 OF 1

5

↑

4

3

2

1

2.5 mm DC Plug: D-0-P1

BOM

NOTES:

1. MATERIALS
 - INSULATING WASHER - PHENOLIC
 - PIN CONTACT - BRASS, NICKEL PLATED
 - BODY - BRASS, NICKEL PLATED
 - INSULATING TUBE - MYLAR
 - PLUG INSULATOR - DELRIN
 - PIN TERMINAL - BRASS, ELECTRO TIN PLATED
 - CLAMP TERMINAL - BRASS, ELECTRO TIN PLATED
 - HANDLE - MOLDED PLASTIC

2. THIS PRODUCT IS RoHS COMPLIANT.

PART NUMBER	HANDLE COLOR
760	BLACK
765	RED

CUSTOMER DRAWING

					★ STAR SYMBOL DENOTES CRITICAL DIMENSION	THIS DRAWING DESCRIBES A DESIGN CONSIDERED PROPRIETARY IN NATURE, DEVELOPED AND MANUFACTURED BY SWITCHCRAFT INC. AND IS RELEASED ON A CONFIDENTIAL BASIS FOR IDENTIFICATION PURPOSES ONLY.				
					UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED	SIZE	WIDTH	MULT	LBS/M	TEMPER
					1. ALL DIMENSIONS IN INCHES - TWO PLACE DECIMALS ±0.01 - THREE PLACE DECIMALS ±0.005 - ANGLES ±1° - ALL DIA. CONCENTRIC WITHIN 0.005 T.I.R.	FINISH		MATERIAL		
					2. FEATURES ON THE SAME CENTERLINE MUST BE ALIGNED WITHIN ±0.002	SPEC No.		SPEC No.		
					3. REMOVE ALL BURRS	FIRST USED ON		SCALE 3:1		
C	REDRAWN ECO#23911	5-31-07	TJK	TJK	DATE DRAWN	BY	CHKD	APVD	Switchcraft®	
REV	ECO NUMBER	DATE	BY	APVD	5-27-87	LSP	EB 5-27-87	RV 5-27-87		
REVISIONS					DO NOT SCALE DRAWING	NAME			PART No.	
						POWER PLUG, RoHS			760-765	
									SHEET 1 OF 1	
									REV C	

Pro/Engineer CAD File

CV